

TOWARDS
A NATIONAL
COLLECTION

Arts and
Humanities
Research Council

FINAL REPORT

DISCOVERY PROJECTS

***Our Heritage, Our Stories:* Linking and
searching Community-Generated
Digital Content**

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
Abstract	5
Aims and Objectives	6
Partnership Structure	8
Core Partners	8
Collaborating Partners	8
Community Partners.....	10
Data Contributors	10
Research Collaborators	11
Workshop Collaborators	12
Staffing Structure	14
Overall Programme	16
Events and Consultations	18
Research Approach	30
Archives Lab.....	30
AI Lab and Linguistics Workstream	33
Observatory Lab.....	36
History Lab.....	38
Research Results	39
Community-Generated Digital Content.....	39
Data Linking	42
Data Use and Reuse	44
Data Sharing on Research Projects.....	50
Post-Custodial Model.....	51

Project Outputs	53
Pipeline (D1)	53
Observatory (D2)	53
Remixer Tools (D3).....	53
CGDC Research Studies (D5)	56
Post-Custodial Toolkit (D6)	57
White papers (D7).....	57
Workshops.....	57
Other Outputs.....	58
Cross Project Collaboration	59
Sustainability and Infrastructure	60
AI Pipeline (D1)	60
Observatory (D2)	60
Remixer Tools (D3).....	60
OHOS Community Heritage Wikibase (D4).....	61
Peer-reviewed Publications (D5).....	61
Post-Custodial Toolkit (D6)	61
White Papers (D7).....	63
CPD Activities.....	63
Workshop Reports.....	63
Community Fund	63
Project Website	64
Grey Literature.....	64
Final Recommendations	65
Archival Recommendations	65
Recommendations for Researchers Working with CGDC Materials	67
Technical Recommendations	68
Structural/Systemic Recommendations	69

Recommendations for Future Projects	70
Contacts.....	71
References	72

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Front cover images:

Letter from Lillie Joly, Seoul, [Korea], to Lady Laura Vaughan Williams 30 Nov 1913. Reproduced by permission of Surrey History Centre.

Dynamic network visualisation illustrating the relationships among entities extracted from the archive metadata using the NLP pipeline.

Kinloch Historical Society Community-Generated Archive. 'S.S City of Karachi 1957, Mary and James, Sydney'. Source: Lorna Hughes.

Executive Summary

Project Overview

Our Heritage, Our Stories (OHOS) represents the most extensive investigation to date of UK Community-Generated Digital Content (CGDC), outlining potential mechanisms for bringing complex data from across the broader heritage landscape into a future UK national collection. This three-year project, involving over twenty researchers at the Universities of Glasgow and Manchester and The National Archives of the UK, and more than a hundred partner and community organisations, developed innovative approaches to preserve, connect, remix, and share diverse community-created digital heritage materials, addressing the critical challenge of integrating these valuable but endangered cultural assets into the UK's national collection.

Research Context and Objectives

CGDC represents a vital yet vulnerable component of the UK's cultural heritage, encompassing born-digital or digitised content created by and for communities. The project responded to the urgent challenges that make CGDC 'critically endangered': it is scattered among a variety of organisations beyond the well-known mainstream of heritage organisations, with its creators and custodians equipped with limited financial, technological and legal means to make this content available online in a user-friendly way, to link it with existing databases, or to integrate their data into much larger datasets. The importance of CGDC is that when communities take control of documenting their own experiences and knowledge, they create vital threads in the fabric of our national collection. As communities capture and share their own stories, they strengthen and sustain their cultural identity. In CGDC, we find dynamic spaces where elders and young digital natives can connect, ensuring endangered traditional knowledge finds new forms of record in the digital age. Through community-led archives, groups can show how their stories evolve and remain relevant, while preserving their dialects and languages as they are actually used. By empowering communities to be the custodians of their own stories, we ensure that future generations inherit not just historical records but living, breathing cultural legacies that continue to inform and inspire. However, its nature as a distributed and generally underfunded resource means that CGDC has a significant resistance to traditional methods of linking and integration, which limits its accessibility so dramatically that such content risks being not only undervalued but overlooked. This is all the more problematic because CGDC is critical not only to completing and complementing the nation's official historical record, but also to correcting and even contradicting it, by allowing otherwise unheard voices to speak, which in turn provides researchers and the wider public access to less familiar stories, alternative perspectives and marginalised experiences. A vast amount of commitment, trust, passion, labour, and public funding has gone into the generation of these precious materials. Rather than allow these efforts to slip away into disuse, we should celebrate CGDC and support the communities who create it, share it, and are represented by it.

Recognising the importance of CGDC and its vulnerability and inaccessibility in an effective, easily reproducible and cost-efficient way has been a key OHOS objective. Existing solutions to CGDC integration, involving bespoke interventionist activities, proved expensive, time-consuming, and unsustainable at scale. Our approach, by contrast, consisted of a collaboration between multiple disciplines and institutions towards the development of new methods involving Artificial Intelligence-based tools to allow for the harmonisation

of CGDC metadata. This harmonisation, in turn, has laid the foundation for bringing previously ‘unfindable’ and/or ‘unlinkable’ CGDC into the UK’s growing virtual national collection; a necessary and timely integration as more and more data is preserved and consumed in digital form.

Specifically, OHOS’s primary objectives included, first, the development of methods to make CGDC discoverable and linking online using AI and emerging approaches. A second major goal concerned the creation of AI-generated Knowledge Graphs for semantic mapping and representation purposes. Thirdly, we designed and delivered targeted computational interventions to integrate various types and collections of CGDC and to make it searchable. Establishing post-custodial frameworks for community-led archive management was a fourth key objective. Finally, the OHOS team built the framework and protocols for sustainable partnerships between different communities and institutions.

Structure

The project was delivered via five interconnected labs. The Archives Lab developed the data strategy, scoped the UK landscape of CGDC for the first time, and developed the post-custodial frameworks. The AI Lab built the natural language processing pipeline for enrichment and streamlining of CGDC metadata. The Observatory Lab created the public-facing infrastructure for accessing CGDC alongside the collections of The National Archives. The History Lab conducted studies on the significance and use of CGDC collections. The Linguistics workstream analysed the language patterns present in CGDC and their relevance to digital processing of CGDC.

Principal Findings

Nature and Value of CGDC

OHOS has established that CGDC represents authentic community voices, which can and must serve to fill crucial gaps in mainstream historical narratives. The project also finds that existing collections vary widely in scale, ranging from small-scale family legacies to documentation covering major global events. Crucially, CGDC often preserves aspects of community history not documented otherwise or elsewhere, making it both unique and all the more invaluable. CGDC also appears in very heterogenous formats resulting from, and tailored to specific community needs.

Heritage Innovation

Heritage is about stories. Understanding the relationship between stories and the language and terms used to describe these stories, and ensuring this rich data in stories is communicated and retained in the documentation of the digital content maintained by archives is a vitally important part of the information lifecycle. OHOS has identified ways that stories can be captured in decentralised approaches to documentation and description, expressed in the post-custodial model of empowering communities to be the custodians in ways that connect tangible material culture to the place, identity, memories and narratives that give it meaning. However, OHOS has identified severe and structural resource constraints that affect most community heritage organisations. A lack of sustained funding for digital preservation threatens the survival of much CGDC in the medium and long term, requiring mitigating action. The project has also documented the manifold legal and ethical considerations complicating digital preservation, data integration

and interlinking, particularly in terms of the strict requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) framework. Finally, OHOS has charted the various trust barriers and power differentials that exist between communities and established national heritage institutions.

Technical Innovation

OHOS has demonstrated the viability and practicability of linking diverse datasets while preserving community autonomy, exemplified in our AI pipeline for the automated enrichment of CGDC metadata: a model that could be rolled out more broadly across the range of UK holdings to encompass a truly national collection.

Further, the output of the AI pipeline is an important testbed of born-digital data that is complex, rich, hybrid, and potentially multilingual, multidialectal, and multimodal. This output has been used to build the Observatory, for sophisticated Knowledge Graphs that enable cross-collection navigation and discovery, for advanced visualisations, and to populate a Wikibase for community heritage. As a dataset, it will also be incredibly valuable as the basis for further development of AI in particular, and digital innovation more broadly. Currently, CGDC data can't be used for AI development as it is not open: the OHOS model for making this data open and re-useable in a harmonised way creates an important new body of born-digital data that was previously inaccessible.

Infrastructural Innovation

The project has successfully made a production-grade workflow for CGDC that leverages existing infrastructure and delivery platforms at The National Archives, highlighting how solutions and skills in digital data can be developed and scaled up to be slotted into a national collection for the UK. This is an important innovation exemplar of how the UK's creative industries can be world-leading, showcasing the best of its creativity and culture to the world. OHOS has successfully researched and implemented a legal and procedural workflow that ties community archives into a wider context whilst maintaining their ownership and agency of their own material: a significant achievement in itself, that also signposts development that supports the UK's innovation agenda, specifically addressing key areas for successful growth in the creative industries, enabling not just the need for better and more effective use and re-use of complex heritage data at scale by national organisations, but identifying existing and emerging strengths of small and local heritage organisations that make a disproportionate contribution to wellbeing, inclusion, and developing capabilities across the regions.

Critical Recommendations

Funding and Infrastructure

1. Establish sustained and reliable funding mechanisms for community heritage organisations that supports their digital ambitions.
2. Create a national digital infrastructure supporting CGDC preservation that recognises its importance as a national asset.

3. Develop robust and cooperative infrastructure frameworks that support digital collaboration and innovation around re-useable and repurposable collections of CGDC.

Technical Development

1. Implement privacy-first design in automated systems.
2. Create standards for maintaining and re-ingesting CGDC data over time.
3. Improve AI tools for handling personal data in diverse formats.

Policy and Practice

1. Adopt post-custodial approaches empowering community control of archives.
2. Establish transparent GDPR guidelines for the heritage sector.
3. Create a national registry of CGDC resources.

Abstract

Community-generated digital content (CGDC) is a precious cultural resource that can complement, correct and contradict the existing historical record. However, this rich and important content created by and for communities is digitally fragile: it is fragmented and difficult to access and preserve due to technological and organisational barriers. The challenges of integrating CGDC into larger archives have effectively silenced diverse community voices within the UK's national collection.

Our Heritage, Our Stories (OHOS) responded to those challenges by bringing together cutting-edge approaches from cultural heritage, the humanities, and computer science. By engaging with communities and institutional partners nationwide, OHOS mapped out the specific nature and the various barriers standing in the way of citizen access to CGDC. The project created integrated access to born-digital and digitised CGDC collections through an innovative public-facing Observatory at The National Archives, while producing user-friendly tools for remixing and re-using data, allowing it to be visualised as Knowledge Graphs. OHOS created ground-breaking technical, organisational, legal, and procedural frameworks for data management of complex CGDC. Our significant achievement offers a blueprint for how to tie community archives into a wider context of greater accessibility and usefulness whilst simultaneously assuring said archives' ownership of and control over their content. Addressing key areas for innovation and growth in the UK's creative industries, OHOS enables improved use and re-use of complex heritage data at scale by national organisations while identifying the strengths of small and local heritage organisations that disproportionately contribute to wellbeing, inclusion, and developing capabilities across the regions.

Aims and Objectives

- Situate community-held and community-generated digital content (CGDC) as part of a national collection: make it discoverable and linkable using existing and emerging approaches, including AI, and create a post-custodial approach to discovering and managing community-generated content. We will leverage the full range of our partnerships' strengths to do this, via a set of integrated Labs that utilise the project team's wide-ranging experience and expertise.
- Undertake an extensive and collaborative programme of research to build semantic mapping and representation of CGDC via AI-generated Knowledge Graphs. Through research into the information ecosystems of CGDC, including its creation, description and management, we will scope the full range and complexity of this content across the UK to understand its linguistic and cultural diversity and richness, including the use of community languages, dialects, and expressions to authentically describe entities, experiences, and content.
- Deliver a series of computational and infrastructural interventions that will make CGDC searchable and discoverable, and break down existing silos. These include co-designing and building an AI 'pipeline' to assess, harvest, and integrate large amounts of CGDC data into our Observatory at The National Archives (TNA); tools to semantically link this content to the collections of TNA and beyond, including complementary collections held by community-facing bodies, especially local museums, archives, and heritage organisations; and the production of 'generous interfaces' offering rich, browsable views that make clear context and relationships between collections, co-designed with CGDC creators and holders.
- Build and implement a sophisticated project framework that is at the cutting edge of linking digital collections and which leverages existing resources, platforms, and technologies, including TNA's Discovery catalogue system and Manage Your Collections platform, to visualise, remix, and share CGDC.
- Develop and disseminate research studies showcasing the value of remixing, enriching, and reusing CGDC for new cross-disciplinary and cross-collection research questions that would be impossible to formulate or address without a unified approach to the content.
- Use these studies to undertake an extensive process of vibrant and inclusive public engagement with stakeholders representing a broad and truly national cross-section of all aspects of community heritage. This includes collecting institutions; local archives and historical societies working with community-facing content; archival and collecting professional associations; specialist subject networks, including teaching and training networks; and individuals and community groups creating and using CGDC.

- Share innovative methods and exchange findings across the TaNC programme and beyond in order to co-develop best practice, discover potential new collaborations, and engage with the wider questions of a national collection.
- Exemplify new ways of understanding 'citizen history', while diversifying and extending audiences, centring and amplifying previously marginalised voices.
- Co-design and prototype post-custodial models of archive management with partner and collaborating organisations and the extensive community of practice working with this material. A new 'toolkit' will ensure future discovery and use and create liminal and porous connections between communities and collecting organisations, situating community expertise as central to the recording, safeguarding, and communication of their artefacts.
- Produce research outputs on our advances in AI, our new understanding of the language and dialect of community content, the use of CGDC in historical research, our models and toolkit of new post-custodial archival practice, and also release code and documentation for our tools and pipeline.

Partnership Structure

Our Heritage, Our Stories (OHOS) was an interdisciplinary University-IRO collaboration, with a network of collections partners and CGDC stakeholders, as well as organisations at the forefront of linguistic, technical, educational, and digital preservation development.

Core Partners

The University of Glasgow was responsible for the Archives Lab, the Linguistics workstream, and overall project management and allocation of project roles and responsibilities. The University of Manchester was responsible for the History Lab and the AI Lab. The National Archives' (TNA) digital development team delivered the Observatory and remixer tools. Our intersecting 'lab'-based structure fed into the development of our CGDC Observatory, which was the responsibility of TNA.

Collaborating Partners

Collaborating with the University of Glasgow, the University of Manchester, and TNA were the following organisations:

National Library of Scotland (NLS)

NLS provided the project with access to some collections metadata. They also contributed expertise in the areas of community collections, cultural heritage, and digital content management to develop three case studies for the project, feeding into the development of our white papers, and ran a community heritage workshop which was a data-gathering opportunity.

National Library of Wales (NLW)

NLW provided access to community-generated materials within their collections, including People's Collection Wales materials from the NLW collections. Additionally, their specific expertise and extensive experience supported the project in: scoping the methodologies of community content creation by People's Collection Wales staff at NLW; research input from collections staff working on the challenges of collections with community generated content and metadata, including multi-format collections that are hybrid and complex, input on bilingual authority data, and on the challenges of semantic mapping of Welsh language content. They also developed the project's CGDC Wikibase (see below). This will be sustained by NLW as an additional OHOS output.

Public Records Office of Northern Ireland (PRONI)

PRONI supported OHOS by providing access to unique community-generated collections held by PRONI and its network of collaborating archives, contributing to our scoping of the CGDC ecosystem and lifecycle. PRONI also provided expertise in community-generated and community-held archives and collections in digital and born-digital

form, as well as contributing to the development and delivery of key case studies and workshops throughout the course of the project, including a major workshop at PRONI in June 2024 which resulted in a high-level policy document addressing support needs for CGDC in Northern Ireland.

Wikimedia

Wikimedia provided support to OHOS by running a Wikidata Workshop in partnership with NLW, and providing specialist advice on our approach to data linking, including linking multilingual data and the development of an OHOS Wikibase instance for sharing linked open data from the project.

Manchester Histories (working on behalf of Archives+)

Manchester Histories works with a broad range of community groups and archives and contributed to OHOS by scoping community heritage organisations in the North West of England, contributing to our understanding of data and metadata, and providing a number of case studies for our white papers. They also provided their extensive expertise to run workshops with community organisations, contributing to the development of the project's post-custodial model and facilitating greater collaboration with further community groups.

Tate

Tate carried out focused research and development for OHOS, including sharing specific findings from relevant research projects conducted by Tate, especially those engaging with communities working with Tate archives, and scoping practice-led case studies. This input was consolidated in the organisation of a major public-facing workshop at Tate in 2024, called [‘The Archive is a Gathering Place’](#).

Software Sustainability Institute (SSI)

SSI contributed to OHOS through collaborating on key dissemination activities, including developing case studies and input to white papers, which SSI will showcase in their broader community of practice, including cross-disciplinary communities.

Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC)

DPC provided OHOS with specific expertise in the information ecosystem for CGDC and preservation challenges for community heritage. Furthermore, DPC provided access to their diverse global network of members; this gave the project access to extensive expertise in working with community-generated content and challenges of community co-creation, including organisations already using and developing a post-custodial approach. This expert network was used to validate and amplify the research and outputs of the project, creating impacts in broader sectors and geographies than could typically be engaged. The project's Post-Custodial Toolkit was developed and launched in collaboration with DPC, who are hosting this resource over the long term to ensure it is sustained beyond the lifetime of the project.

Association for Learning Technology (ALT)

OHOS was supported by ALT through their sharing of expertise on legal aspects associated with community heritage, including expert peer review of OHOS outputs relating to the digital heritage of community organisations; and advice about future digital training and development that can disseminate OHOS outputs. ALT also advised on the use of ALT's Accreditation Framework for Learning Technology, CMALT, to embed project research and outcomes in academic programmes in archives and community history.

National Lottery Heritage Fund (NLHF)

NLHF contributed their expertise in collaborating and engaging with community heritage to OHOS, as well as their experience in managing and sustaining CGDC. This supported OHOS in community engagement activities and organisation of the project community fund. A white paper identifying key areas of intervention by NLHF in support of sustaining CGDC was created.

Dictionaries of the Scots Language (DSL)

DSL provided the project with licensed access to the full data of DSL, the national record of the Scots language from the twelfth century onwards, with over 75,000 entries (including definitions, quotations, and variant spellings), and expertise. This data was implemented to improve the automated approaches of the AI Lab and Linguistics workstream in interpreting multilingual CGDC.

Historical Thesaurus of English (HT)

HT provided OHOS with licensed access to the full data of HT, the largest ontology in existence of concepts recorded in the English language over the last thousand years, including dialect forms, with over 800,000 words recorded in over 250,000 categories. This data was implemented to improve the automated approaches of the AI Lab and Linguistics workstream in interpreting CGDC. HT also provided their expertise in historical and multilingual data, natural language processing, and complex conceptual ontologies.

Community Partners

A wide array of community organisations collaborated with the OHOS project, beyond those originally included as partner organisations in the project bid. These organisations contributed data, expertise, feedback, and time towards project progress and outputs.

Data Contributors

Several community organisations contributed CGDC to the project, allowing this data to be enriched using the project's AI pipeline and where appropriate displayed alongside Discovery materials in the OHOS Observatory. The community partner archives were:

- Conflict Archive on the INternet (CAIN)

- Milton Keynes City Discovery Centre
- People’s Collection Wales (PCW)
- Sharing Wycombe's Old Photographs (SWOP)
- Surrey History Centre
- The Morrab Library

Research Collaborators

Numerous community organisations contributed to the OHOS project’s research activities, supporting the project’s work documenting CGDC creation and curation practices, mapping the lifecycle of CGDC, and developing a post-custodial framework to support communities in the management of their materials. This included contributions to research interviews, reports and white papers. The community partners who supported project research were:

- Acid House Flashback
- African Stories in Hull and East Yorkshire
- After the Garden Festival...
- Beyond the Point
- Chatteris Community Archive
- Cinema sgire
- East Riding of Yorkshire Council Museums and Archives Service
- Endangered Knowledge Material Programme (EMKP)
- History Hub Ulster
- Hull Bullnose Heritage Group
- International Bomber Command Centre
- Kingston Centre for Independent Living
- Leas Pavilion Archive
- Manchester Histories
- Milton Keynes City Discovery Centre
- Modus Arts
- National Disability Arts Collection
- National Disability Arts Collection & Archive (NDACA)
- Newport History Group’s Website and Archive
- Northern Ireland Community Archive
- OurStory Scotland
- Pirton Local History Archive
- Played in a Band
- Remembering the past
- Scarborough Maritime Heritage Group
- Scope’s 'Speaking for Ourselves: An Oral History of People with Cerebral Palsy'
- St Andrew's Dock Heritage Action Group
- St Neots Cambridgeshire Community Archive Network
- Steeple Aston Village Archive (SAVA)
- Tandana- the Glowworm

- The Badsey Society's Archive
- The Debenham Archive
- The Russian Arctic Convoy Museum
- The Weaving the Web project - Sunny Bank Mills Archive
- Tiger Bay Collection - The Heritage & Cultural Exchange
- WE: The Ex-Warner Estate in Waltham Forest

Workshop Collaborators

A wide array of community organisations also contributed to the OHOS project's workshop activities, supporting the project's community engagement and dissemination work through attending and/or presenting at project workshops. These community partners were:

- Art 360 Foundation
- Cardinal Tomás Ó Fiaich Memorial Library and Archive
- CollabArchive
- Columbia University Archives
- Community Archives and Heritage Group (CAHG)
- Conflict Archive on the INternet (CAIN)
- Cupar Museum and Heritage Centre
- Cyberfeminism Index
- Digital Repository of Ireland
- Friends of Platt Fields
- George Hallett Research Collection
- Glasgow Building Preservation Trust
- Glasgow Zine Library
- Govanhill Baths
- Greater Manchester Coalition for Disabled People
- House of Dread
- June Givanni Pan African Cinema Archive
- Lauren Craig Studios
- Lavender Menace Queer Books
- Manchester Digital Music Archive
- Manchester Hip-Hop Archive
- MayDayRooms
- Mellon Centre for Migration Studies
- National Lottery Heritage Fund NI
- Nerve Centre
- Northern Ireland History Society
- Northern Ireland Screen
- Paisley Heritage
- Palestine Literature Archive
- Panchayat Collection

- Prisons Memory Archive
- Queens University Belfast
- Rita Keegan Studio
- rukus!
- Rural Community Network
- SITAAD
- Stornoway Historical Society
- The John and Pat Hume Foundation
- The Women's Art Library
- Thread Maiden
- UAL Decolonising Arts Institute
- Ulster Human Rights Watch
- Whose Knowledge?

Staffing Structure

Overall project leadership was situated at the University of Glasgow, where the project PI, Deputy PI, and Project Manager roles were based. There were initially two fractional PDRAs at Glasgow (in archives and linguistics/project management); this was expanded to include a full-time project manager, and replacement PDRAs in later years of the project, as well as a full-time Project Officer in the final six months of the project.

At the University of Manchester, there were three Co-Is, two in the AI Lab and one in the History Lab. Each of these Labs had one full-time PDRA for the duration of the project, with staffing for these roles detailed below. At The National Archives, the team initially comprised five people: a Co-I, a delivery manager, and three research software engineers. This Observatory Lab team was responsible for delivering the final public-facing project Observatory but in the final year of the project, the delivery model for the Observatory was changed and the Observatory developed by a different team at TNA, as detailed below.

Investigators

- Prof Lorna Hughes (Principal Investigator, University of Glasgow) oversaw and managed the project with responsibility for budget oversight, partner management and liaison, risks, and contingencies, in addition to leading the Archives Lab and drawing together the archival and infrastructural elements of the project.
- Prof Marc Alexander (University of Glasgow) deputised and supported Hughes in project management, and led the work in the Linguistics workstream, particularly in the areas of multilingual and multidialectal inclusion and variation, computational linguistics, and language ontologies.
- Pip Willcox (The National Archives) led the Observatory Lab and coordinated the TNA input to the project from September 2021 to July 2023.
- John Sheridan (The National Archives) led the Observatory Lab from August 2023 onwards, and as the Digital Director for TNA led the Observatory development and release.
- Prof Hannah Barker (University of Manchester) led the History Lab, overseeing and designing the scoping and use of CGDC to build research capacity.
- Prof Goran Nenadic (University of Manchester) led the AI Lab and was responsible for the overall design and implementation of the AI pipeline.
- Dr Riza Batista-Navarro (University of Manchester) led the design of Natural Language Processing tools and methods within the AI Lab.

Managers

- Dr Ewan Hannaford (University of Glasgow) was part-time Project Manager from September 2021 to June 2023, responsible for overall project planning, project liaison with TaNC programme activities, partner relationships, and PI support.
- Hazel Jell (The National Archives) was Agile Delivery Manager at TNA, co-ordinating delivery of the project Observatory, from January 2022 to February 2023. From February 2023 to July 2023, her

role became Senior Agile Delivery Manager to also include cross-Lab collaborative planning and data management.

- Rebecka Rosenberg (University of Glasgow) was hired as full-time Project Manager between June 2023 and July 2024 as additional project management capacity was required. She took over responsibility for overall programme delivery and workplan implementation, as well as heritage partner management.
- Nella McNicol (University of Glasgow) was hired as Project Officer from June 2024 to January 2025 to assist with administrative and planning activities on the project, as well as contributing to work in the Archives Lab. She took over the majority of Project Manager responsibilities in the period between Rebecka Rosenberg's departure in July 2024 and Katrien Dierckx's arrival in November 2024.
- Dr Katrien Dierckx (University of Glasgow) was hired as full-time Project Manager for the final months of the project from November 2024 to January 2025.

Research Assistants/Associates and Research Software Engineers

- **History Lab:** Dr Stefan Ramsden (University of Manchester) was research assistant within the History Lab from September 2022 to September 2024, contributing to identifying and engaging community archives, and developing the project's post-custodial model for community archival management. Dr Jessica Hammett was research assistant in the History Lab from October 2021 to August 2022.
- **Archives Lab:** Dr Abi L. Glen (University of Glasgow) was research assistant for the Archives Lab from August 2023 to January 2025, researching community archives and post-custodial frameworks, disseminating these frameworks, and identifying and liaising with existing and prospective community archive partners. In addition to her administrative activities, Nella McNicol also contributed to the research and outputs of the Archives Lab from June 2024 to January 2025. Previous research assistants in this lab were Dr Diane Scott, from September 2021 to October 2022, and Rhiannon Lewis, from January 2023 to May 2024.
- **AI Lab:** Dr Youcef Benkhedda (University of Manchester) was research associate within the AI Lab for the final two years of the project from October 2022 to January 2025, developing the automated approaches to ingesting, processing, and enriching community-generated digital content. Dr Viktor Schlegel was research assistant in this lab for the first year of the project, leaving in October 2022.
- **Linguistics workstream:** Dr Ewan Hannaford (University of Glasgow) was research assistant working on linguistics-based work (including AI coordination work and multilingual/multidialectal data) from September 2021 to November 2024. Dr Hanna Schmück developed the project's linguistics work and outputs in the final months of the project, from October 2024 to January 2025.
- **Observatory:** Delivery of the Observatory at TNA was originally undertaken by a team of RSEs (Walteri Nybom, Harshad Gupta and Dr Andrew Bewsey) co-ordinated by Hazel Jell as Agile Delivery Manager. In August 2023 the Observatory delivery model was changed, with TNA's Digital Services team taking over delivery until November 2024.

Overall Programme

The project start date was 1 October 2021.

The project ended on 31 January 2025, following two no-cost extensions agreed by AHRC due to delays with recruitment. The funder was kept updated on progress with all deliverables throughout the project.

OHOS workplan overview		
Activity	Start date	End Date
1: Scope and map current community archive practices and barriers	Oct-21	Sep-24
2: Outreach and build community of practice with community archives	Oct-21	Sep-24
3: Develop data sharing agreements with project partners and archives supplying data to the pipeline.	Jun-23	Jan-25
4: Develop processing and enrichment methods for CGDC	Oct-21	Apr-24
D0: Data tranche 0 collection and processing	Nov-21	Jun-22
5: AI pipeline V1 and NLP model development	Nov-21	Jun-22
6: Partner CGDC data gathering for ingest in D1	Dec-21	Aug-23
7: Establish platform & protocols for data sharing across project team	Jan-22	Nov-24
8: Initial research demonstrator case study development (History)	Mar-22	Jan-23
9: Refine CGDC processing/enrichment during AI pipeline development	Jun-22	Feb-24
10: Observatory V1 development	Jun-22	Sep-22
M1: Data tranche 0 processed and AI pipeline V1 developed	Jun-22	
11: AI pipeline V2 development and NLP model revisions	Jul-22	Dec-23
12: Observatory and Manage Your Collections integration	Jul-22	Feb-24
D1: Data tranche 1 collection and processing (low complexity CGDC)	Aug-22	Mar-23
M2: Observatory server online (internal)	Sep-22	
M3: Observatory interface developed (internal)	Sep-22	
C1/C2: Community Fund Calls (Targeted)	May-23	Nov-23
13: Remixer Suite V1 development	Oct-22	May-24
14: Develop model of best practice and dissemination for CGDC	Oct-22	Sep-24
C3: Community Fund targeted calls and projects co-created	Dec-23	Mar-24
15: Produce case studies of community-managed artifacts and collections	Feb-23	Jul-24

M4: AI pipeline V2 developed	Mar-23	
M5: First research demonstrator case studies release	Mar-23	
16: Refinement of CGDC processing methods, inc. linguistic resources	Apr-23	Aug-24
17: AI pipeline V3 development and NLP model revisions	Apr-23	Dec-23
D2: Data Tranche 2 collection and processing (medium complexity CGDC)	May-23	Dec-23
M6: Remixer Suite V1 developed	Apr-24	
M7: Integration of multilingual resources into AI pipeline	Aug-24	
18: Remixer Suite V2 development	Apr-24	May-24
M8: AI pipeline V3 developed	Dec-23	
19: AI pipeline V4 (final) development and refinement	Jan-24	Aug-24
C4: Community Fund targeted calls and projects co-created	Feb-24	Dec-24
D3: Data tranche 3 collection and processing (high complexity CGDC)	Feb-24	Sep-24
M9: Observatory interface finalisation and delivery for partner review	Apr-24	
20: Launch of Observatory, sustainability work	Mar-24	Dec-24
M10: Final set of research demonstrator case studies release	Sep-24	
M11: Release of post-custodial model/toolkit	Nov-24	
M12: AI pipeline V4 (final) completion and release	Aug-24	
M13: Remixer Suite V2 (final) developed and released	Sep-24	
M14: Release of all project documentation	Jan-25	

Events and Consultations

Workshops		
Event/consultation	Dates & participants	Description
Project start-up workshop (W1)	10 th December 2021 London Number of participants: 10	Kick-off workshop to introduce project team in person and discuss project roadmap, including tasks, roles, deliverables, and milestones.
Partner information workshop	21 st June 2022 Online Number of participants: 20	Workshop to update all primary partners (DPC, NLS, NLW, PRONI, SSI, Tate, Wikimedia) on project progress and discuss areas of further collaboration. Followed up with individual partner meetings to outline specific tasks.
Year 2 Kick-Off / Evaluating Reuse workshop (W3)	12 th -14 th October 2022 York Number of participants: 16	This workshop was originally intended to solely focus on how CGDC was (re)used across users, researchers, and producers, and how this fed into project outputs. However, clear differences in project visions meant this workshop primarily focused on aligning understanding of the project aims, objectives, and outputs between the HEIs and our lead IRO partner. This was conducted within a facilitated workshop kicking off our second year on the project, aligning project vision and shared understanding of project goals/outputs.
Historian engagement workshop (W5)	Spring 2023 Manchester Number of participants: 15	Collaboration-centred event involving local and institutional historians, developing project networks, furthering co-design approach, and informing design of historian-focused elements of the project. Run with Manchester Histories/Archives +.
Ethics & Data Sharing Models workshop Attendance at TaNC Ethics Workshop (W8A)	23 rd January 2024 London	Contribution to TaNC's Ethics workshop, which brought together representatives from the Discovery Projects and the TaNC programme Directorate to discuss how ethics are woven into the structures of the projects and share common learnings.
BYO CGDC Datathon Series of 6 activities (W11)	February 2024 Online	Originally intended as a single event where archives would bring their data, due to long-term effects on the sector by covid and the lack of readily available material for the OHOS AI pipeline in MYC/collaborating institutions, this

	Number of participants: 8 participants per data-gathering exercise	was replaced by one-to-one data-gathering exercises with community archives that through close collaboration and engagement with the project decided to include their cataloguing metadata into the creation and development of the Observatory. W11A BYO CGDC Datathon – Milton Keynes City Discovery Centre W11B BYO CGDC Datathon – Sharing Wycombe’s Old Photographs W11C BYO CGDC Datathon – Surrey History Centre W11D BYO CGDC Datathon – People’s Collection Wales W11E BYO CGDC Datathon – The Morrab Library W11F BYO CGDC Datathon – CAIN Archive
Remixing Tools for CGDC workshop (W4)	13 th February 2024 Online Number of participants: 16	Exploratory workshop looking at varying approaches to the ‘remixing’ (i.e. the presentation, analysis, and comparison) of CGDC across diverse archives, materials, and audiences. Conducted as an internal workshop for project team members to discuss visualisation tools for the Observatory.
Ethics & Data Sharing Models Tate focus groups sessions (W8B)	April 2024 London & Online Number of participants: 32	Three focus groups aimed to prepare for the public workshop in May 2024, allowing the project team to garner probable themes and learnings.
CGDC Producers Workshop Connecting community archives (W2A)	23 rd April 2024 Glasgow Number of participants: 19	In conjunction with the Community Archives Heritage Group (CAHG), the National Library of Scotland hosted an event targeted at organiser groups within the sphere of community archiving in Scotland with a focus on case studies. Participating organisations included: Glasgow Zine Library, Paisley Heritage, Cupar Museum, Govanhill Baths, Lavender Menace Queer Books Archive, and Comhairle nan Eilean Siar, Stornoway.
Ethics and data sharing models workshop Tate festival The Archive is a Gathering Place (W8C)	24 th -25 th May 2024 London Number of participants: 200	A two-day festival called ‘The Archive is a Gathering Place’ for the public and Tate networks to discuss and consider that approaches should be included in a truly ethical framework toward the inclusion of historically marginalised materials.
CGDC Producers Workshop What is the Future of CGDC?	11 th June 2024 Belfast	An open event hosted by PRONI and targeted at community groups that hold digital archival material, focused on the current landscape in Northern Ireland and

(W2B)	Number of participants: 37	what challenges exist and what solutions could solve them.
Language data and Wikidata workshop (W9)	16 th July 2024 Online & Twente, The Netherlands Number of participants: approx. 40	This workshop focused on the theme of language data, data ontologies, and digital archives, including reflections on the OHOS project's research around integrating linguistic resources and Wikidata into the processing of CGDC. The hybrid event took the form of a series of talks, followed by a group discussion.
Post-custodial approaches workshop Panel discussion at iPres 2024 International Conference on Digital Preservation (W6A)	17 th September 2024 Ghent, Belgium Number of participants: approx. 100	Emerging from the work the project has done through exploring the challenges of sustaining a large number of small-scale, community-based digitisation initiatives, the panel introduced and reviewed post-custodial models of digital preservation and set them in a global perspective. It facilitated a pre-recorded panel made up of community groups, ensuring that they were represented in the discussion. This provoked comment from the in-person panel of practitioners from different contexts, including from Aotearoa / New Zealand where data sovereignty principles have been impactful in the protection of land, culture and knowledge.
Post-custodial approaches workshop Capturing Language and Dialects and Post-Custodial Practice (W6B)	6 th November 2024 & 9 th January 2025 Online Number of participants: 6	Structured interviews and feedback from the Prisons Memory Archive (PMA), discussing the specifics of building an archive on the lived experience of prisoners at Armagh Gaol and Maze and Long Kesh, Northern Ireland. The holders of the archive also discussed the benefits and challenges of recording material in Gaelic and in the prison's situation-specific dialects. Also, workshop input from Leas Pavillion Archive. This activity contributed to OHOS/W6's aim of developing a post-custodial model for the curation and management of CGDC, via input from diverse stakeholders.
OHOS final symposium World Digital Preservation Day (W12A)	7 th -8 th November 2024 London Number of participants: 42	OHOS final symposium, held in conjunction with the Digital Preservation Coalition. This event launched and celebrated the OHOS post-custodial archival outputs, which will be sustained over the long term.
OHOS final symposium Being Human Festival Community Fund Showcase	9 th November 2024 Glasgow Number of participants: 25	OHOS worked with the Glasgow Building Preservation Trust and The Pipe Factory to host 'Barras Hunt' at Being Human, the UK's premier Arts and Humanities festival. Participants formed teams to purchase an object from the Barras

(W12B)		market which they felt told a story about Glasgow. This formed a guerilla archive. Volunteers from all three organisations explained how everyone can form their own archive and gave a basic introduction to how to begin to (digitally) preserve theirs.
Association for Learning Technology (ALT): Community Heritage and Copyright and post custodial tools (W10A)	January 2025	ALT and OHOS co-designed ALT's input to OHOS, through the provision of expert input to key sections of OHOS deliverables relating to community heritage, including expertise on copyright and rights management of CGDC in the post-custodial toolkit.
AI pipeline: Producers & Users workshop (W7)	15 th January 2025 Cardiff Number of participants: 20	Day-long workshop held in collaboration with People's Collection Wales, National Library of Wales and Wikimedia to present the OHOS AI pipeline, to discuss the possibilities of future use, management and engagement with the Wikibase by community groups, to identify metadata challenges and technology needs and to co-create approaches to using the OHOS AI pipeline and Wikibase in standalone, sustainable ways to support community heritage.
Community Archives and Heritage Group Conference and post custodial tools (W10B))	10 th July 2024 London Number of participants: approx. 90	A collection of archives and heritage professionals presented papers on "keeping community at the heart" of archives and heritage, developing a working group to deliver a series of webinars and scope a <i>Connecting Communities</i> workshop and showcase for heritage professionals, community archives and academics to celebrate and share resources in contemporary archiving practice.
Community Events		
Event/consultation	Dates & participants	Description
Manchester Histories/Archives+ workshop series	1 st September – 1 st November 2023 Manchester Number of participants: 15	Manchester Histories hosted four workshops facilitated by their Community Archivist to reveal, share, and celebrate the diverse histories and heritage of Greater Manchester, by exploring various approaches local communities take when dealing with their CGDC. The archive partners were Manchester Hip Hop Archives, Greater Manchester Coalition of Disabled People, Friends of Platt Fields, and Manchester Digital Music Archive.

Glasgow Disability Alliance (GDA) Workshops	13 th January & 18 th April 2024 Glasgow Number of participants: approx. 20	In collaboration with OHOS, GDA ran two events using CGDC materials from their COVID Art Archive. Interviews were held to discuss the process of creating their artwork during the pandemic, allowing participants to explore and reflect on their response to the pandemic, then and now, as disabled people, and how this work can be sustained in the future. These interviews were the basis of two podcast episodes, available on Spotify.
Endangered Materials Knowledge Programme (EMKP), British Museum	17 th March 2024 London Number of participants: 10	EMKP facilitated a one-day workshop hosted at the British Museum in London to assess their digital training guidelines within the wider sector needs identified by OHOS.
National Library of Scotland workshop Connecting Community Archives	23 rd April 2024 Glasgow Number of participants: 25	In conjunction with the Community Archives Heritage Group (CAGH), NLS held a workshop for heritage organisations across Scotland. These included: Glasgow Zine Library, Paisley Heritage, Cupar Museum, Govanhill Baths, Lavender Menace Queer Books Archive, and Comhairle nan Eilean Siar, Stornoway.
Welsh Centre for International Affairs Archiveathon	1 st May 2024 Cardiff Number of participants: 17	WCIA facilitated an Archiveathon to co-create and review WCIA's digital 'Peace Heritage' resources and assess the lifecycle of their creation and preservation. The event involved student and community volunteers. This kicked off a wider Welsh programme of Archiveathons held in May-Sept 2024.
Tate workshops	24 th -25 th May 2024 London Number of participants: 75	Tate hosted a two-day public programme titled <i>The Archive is a Gathering Place</i> , which allowed practitioners to discuss the future of CGDC and collectively owned archives, particularly those created and sustained by artists and artist collectives. The workshops also drew on Tate's existing work in this area, and earlier AHRC funded research projects.
Public Record Office Northern Ireland (PRONI) Workshop	11 th June 2024 Belfast Number of participants: 37	PRONI hosted a day-long workshop entitled <i>What is the Future of CGDC?</i> Participants came from heritage across Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland to discuss this topic, and the specifics of the NI/Irish heritage contexts. A mission statement was also generated for circulation to government and funding bodies, identifying key steps needed to secure the legacy of CGDC across the heritage sector.

CAHG Connecting Community Archives Workshop	14 th June 2024 Edinburgh Number of participants: 12	CAHG conducted an evidence-based investigation of 3 groups, which hold or are working with CGDC in Scotland. These included Colinton Local History Society, Now!, Edinburgh Caribbean Society, Leith Forever, The Living Memory Association, and Portobello Heritage Trust. This workshop explored their working practices, the challenges of working with this type of material, and to highlight current practice. A report has been generated.
Glasgow Building Preservation Trust (GBPT) Workshops + Wiki Walks	1 st & 18 th July 2024 Glasgow Number of participants: 26	In collaboration with OHOS and two other special interest groups (GDA and Migrant Voices), GBPT arranged Wiki Walk workshops. These encouraged participants to capture images across the city while addressing geographic gaps, specific buildings and monuments. These were then reviewed, selected and uploaded by participants onto Wikimedia Commons, who learned how to document their own views on the city, including metadata and quality descriptions. An instructional film was created as a final output with Wikimedia. As a follow-on, GBPT will be hosting an exhibition of the groups' work at the Centre for Creative Arts and during Glasgow Open Days Festival.
Glasgow Artists Moving Image Studios (GAMIS; now known as Offline) Workshop	8 th & 15 th August 2024 Glasgow Number of participants: 10	GAMIS/Offline held two workshops with the artist Mina Heydari-Waite, with the aim of uncovering the potential of minority community archives and their digital presence through filmmaking. The finished film functions as an example of how archival material can be used and re-used to support new forms of access, and digital durability.
The Pipe Factory Business Archives Workshop	23 rd August 2024 Glasgow Number of participants: 6	For volunteers of the Pipe Factory, OHOS facilitated an Introduction to Business Archives session through the Scottish Business Collection based at the University of Glasgow to refine the volunteer's skills and prepare them for their upcoming digital archival projects. The Pipe Factory also hosted the OHOS contribution to the Being Human 2024, with the community event <i>Barras Hunt</i> (09/11/24).
Outer Hebrides Heritage Forum (OHHF) Workshop	29 th October 2024 Isle of Lewis Number of participants: 25	A half-day workshop with the OHHF, who are an umbrella organisation for community heritage groups in the Outer Hebrides, discussing the practicalities of digital archiving and preservation.
Kinloch Historical Society Workshop	27 th -31 st October 2024 Isle of Lewis	OHOS met with members of the team at Kinloch Historical Society as part of a process of co-production of a full digital lifecycle for CGDC held by the Kinloch Historical Society in

	Number of participants: 11	Balallan, Isle of Lewis. This was designed to be open to community and volunteer input at each stage in the digital lifecycle: selection, digitisation, description, preservation, and use, enabling a sustainable model for creating a community held digital archive.
The John & Pat Hume Foundation Quite Peacebuilders event	26 th November 2024 Derry, NI Number of participants: approx. 25	In collaboration with OHOS, The John and Pat Hume Foundation facilitated activities which promote the creation, curation and dissemination of CGDC. Through these activities, the centre has developed an archive/reading room where the legacy of John and Pat Hume, including a physical archive of papers, speeches, letters are preserved, interrogated and analysed. An event to celebrate those who shared their stories took place in November 2024.
Mellon Centre for Migration Studies & Rural Community Network project	November 2024 - January 2025 Belfast, Omagh Number of participants: approx. 25	The Mellon Centre for Migration Studies worked alongside the Rural Community Network to host an outreach and development workshop in December 2024, bringing together migrant and rural communities from across Northern Ireland to discuss and undertake CGDC creation activities on the theme of Home. A final showcase event took place in January 2025.

Academic Events

Event/consultation	Dates & participants	Description
'Linking, sharing and using community generated digital content: using and sustaining citizen histories' University of Michigan Digital Humanities Center	22 nd November 2021 Audience – International, approx. 50	Invited presentation given by PI Lorna Hughes at the University of Michigan Digital Humanities Center. The talk led to networking opportunities and further chances to explore the topics of the OHOS project, which had just started.
'Why Digitise? What can be done, and what can be done differently?' RSE Scottish Magazines Network	24 th June 2021 Audience – National, approx. 20	Paper presentation by PI Lorna Hughes at online event <i>Future Issues: Digitising Twentieth-Century Magazines</i> organised by the Scottish Magazines Network. The presentation explored key principles and opportunities in magazine digitisation.

<p>'Our Heritage Our stories: Linking and searching community-generated digital content to develop the people's national collection'</p> <p>All-Party Parliamentary Committee on Archives</p>	<p>16th November 2021</p> <p>Audience – National, approx. 12</p>	<p>Presentation by PI Lorna Hughes, who was invited to speak at the All-Party Parliamentary Committee on Archives in Westminster.</p>
<p>Keynote lecture for Maltese national MEMORJA project launch</p>	<p>27th November 2021</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 75</p>	<p>Keynote lecture given by Pip Willcox at the MEMORJA seminar held at the University of Malta following the launch of the National Oral Sound and Vision Archive's website (MEMORJA). The lecture explored digital public engagement with archival collections, including through citizen research and through co-designing automated methods of linking CGDC to more established collections.</p>
<p>'Our Stories, in Our Words: Exploring language varieties in the Our Heritage, Our Stories project'</p> <p>Presentation at PALA 2022 Conference</p>	<p>6th-9th July 2022</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 30</p>	<p>Presentation by Linguistics workstream (Ewan Hannaford and Marc Alexander) at the PALA 2022 conference at Aix-Marseille University, France. This talk focused on the linguistic benefits of the project in making accessible the wealth of currently undiscoverable and unsearchable CGDC in the UK, as well as showcasing the project to an international academic audience.</p>
<p>Poster presentation on technical approaches at the Digital Humanities at Oxford University Summer School 2022</p>	<p>10th-15th July 2022</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 200</p>	
<p>'One step up: using digital humanities to bring community generated digital content into a national collection'</p>	<p>10th-15th July 2022</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 200</p>	<p>Keynote lecture by PI Lorna Hughes at the Digital Humanities Summer School at Oxford University.</p>
<p>'Our Heritage, Our Stories: Methods and Models for Working with Community Generated Digital Content'</p>	<p>8th-10th September 2022</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 70</p>	<p>Presentation by Lorna Hughes, Diane Scott, and Ewan Hannaford at the Digital Humanities Congress held in Sheffield.</p>

Presentation at Digital Humanities Congress 2022 conference		
‘Integrating language varieties in the Our Heritage, Our Stories project’ Presentation at Data & Digital Humanities 2023 conference	8 th -10 th March 2023 Audience – International, approx. 15	Presentation by Linguistics workstream (Ewan Hannaford and Marc Alexander) at the DDHUM 2023 conference at the University of Minho, Portugal. This talk focused on the challenges and benefits of integrating diverse linguistic varieties into institutional collections, drawing on work on OHOS as a case study.
‘Linguistic variation and institutional collections’ Language & Power 2023 (LAP2023) conference	22 nd -24 th March 2023 Audience – International, approx. 40	Presentation by Linguistics workstream (Ewan Hannaford and Marc Alexander) at the LAP 2023 conference at the University of Münster, Germany. This talk focused on the potential impacts of diverse linguistic varieties in institutional collections on linguistic prejudice and language equity, drawing on work on OHOS as a case study.
‘Our Heritage, Our Stories: Linking and searching community-generated digital content to develop the people’s national collection’ History and Archives in Practice Conference	29 th March 2023 Audience - International, approx. 60	Presentation by History Lab (Hannah Barker and Stefan Ramsden) at the HAP2023 conference at the Institute of Historical Research, London. This talk focused on the role of CGDC in historical research.
‘IIIF4Research: Understanding researchers use of IIIF’ 2023 International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) Annual conference	5 th -8 th June 2023 Audience - International, approx. 230	Paper presentation by PI Lorna Hughes at the IIIF International Conferences in Naples, Italy.
‘Our Heritage, Our Stories: bringing community (oral) histories to the centre of the national collection’ Oral History Society conference	24 th June 2023 Audience – International, approx. 40	Presentation by the History Lab (Stefan Ramsden) at the Oral History Society conference at Nottingham Trent University. This talk focused on the wealth of oral historical evidence available as CGDC, and the ethical and practical issues involved in the use of this material.

<p>'Our Heritage, Our Stories' and the Postmemory of the Second World War</p> <p>Family Archives and their Afterlives conference</p>	<p>27th June 2023</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 50</p>	<p>Online presentation by the History Lab (Stefan Ramsden) at the Family Archives and their Afterlives conference organised by the University of Birmingham. This presentation focused on how CGDC archives can be used to shed light on the intergenerational transmission of memories in the Second World War.</p>
<p>'Collections as corpora: Insights from Our Heritage, Our Stories' Corpus Linguistics 2023</p>	<p>3rd-6th July 2023</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 60</p>	<p>Presentation by Linguistics workstream (Ewan Hannaford and Marc Alexander) at the Corpus Linguistics 2023 conference at the University of Lancaster on the value of community content for corpus linguistic research and how such materials might be best represented.</p>
<p>Poster presentation at the ADHO Digital Humanities 2023 Conference</p>	<p>10th-14th July 2023</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 200</p>	
<p>'Community discourse and climate: Insights from Our Heritage, Our Stories'</p> <p>PALA 2023 conference</p>	<p>12th-16th July 2023</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 60</p>	<p>Presentation by Linguistics workstream (Ewan Hannaford and Marc Alexander) at the PALA 2023 conference in Bologna (Italy) on the potential influence of community content and wider social behaviours/impacts.</p>
<p>'Re-assessing the digitization lifecycle: digital humanities research and practice in cultural heritage digital projects'</p> <p>First edition of the Digital Authoring of the Berlin Collections in the Jagiellonian Library – Challenges and Perspectives conference</p>	<p>23rd-24th November 2023</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 50</p>	<p>Presentation by OHOS PI Lorna Hughes at the Digital Authoring of the Berlin Collections in the Jagiellonian Library Conference at the Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Poland.</p>
<p>'Collecting dialects: Institutional collections, community archives, and linguistic diversity'</p> <p>ICAME45 conference</p>	<p>18th-22nd June 2024</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 60</p>	<p>Presentation by Linguistics workstream (Ewan Hannaford and Marc Alexander) at ICAME45 in Vigo (Spain) on the diversification of linguistic resources using CGDC.</p>

<p>'Black and Asian Stories of Working-Class Community'</p> <p>Working Class Studies Association Conference</p>	<p>26th June 2024</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 20</p>	<p>Online presentation by the History Lab (Stefan Ramsden) at the Working-Class Studies Association Conference organised by Stony Brook University, New York. This talk focused on the value of CGDC as a source for exploring the history of race relations in working-class communities in 20th-century Britain.</p>
<p>'Linguistics, AI, and Archives: Hybrid approaches on the Our Heritage, Our Stories project'</p> <p>PALA 2024 conference</p>	<p>26th-29th June 2024</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 70</p>	<p>Presentation by Linguistics workstream (Ewan Hannaford and Marc Alexander) at the PALA conference organised by Sheffield Hallam University on hybrid approaches developed collaboratively by the linguistic and computer science teams on the OHOS project to improve NLP approaches to understanding the discourse of community archival materials.</p>
<p>Community Archives and Heritage Group Conference</p>	<p>10th July 2024</p> <p>Audience – National, approx. 100</p>	<p>A collection of archives and heritage professionals presented papers on “keeping community at the heart” of archives and heritage.</p>
<p>'Refining predicates for relation extraction through Thesaurus integration'</p> <p>Formal Ontology in Information Systems Conference 2024</p>	<p>16th July 2024</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 50</p>	<p>Presentation by the AI Lab (Riza Batista-Navarro) at the Formal Ontology in Information Systems Conference 2024 at the University of Twente, Netherlands. The presentation focused on how thesaurus-based predicates can help refine relation extraction techniques for CGDC.</p>
<p>'One step up: the importance of failure in a large-scale DH project at the crossroads of disciplines and institutions'</p>	<p>6th-9th August 2024</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 120</p>	<p>Presentation by PI Lorna Hughes and Deputy PI Marc Alexander at the international DH conference in the USA on the OHOS project, the nature of multi-institutional work and on the importance of discussing and celebrating organisational challenges.</p>
<p>'Remembering the Fishing: Commemorating Coastal Communities Online'</p> <p>IMHA Congress of Maritime History</p>	<p>19th-24th August 2024</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 25</p>	<p>Presentation by History Lab (Stefan Ramsden) at the IMHA Congress of Maritime History in South-Korea. This talk focused on the value of CGDC as source material for maritime historians interested in the history of coastal communities and memories of deindustrialisation.</p>

<p>'Relation Extraction for Constructing Knowledge Graphs: Enhancing the Searchability of Community-Generated Digital Content (CGDC) Collections'</p> <p>7th Edition of Workshop on Deep Learning and Large Language Models for Knowledge Graphs</p>	<p>16th September 2024</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 100</p>	<p>Presentation by the AI Lab (Riza Batista-Navarro) at the Workshop on Deep Learning and Large Language Models for Knowledge Graphs in Barcelona, Spain. This paper explored using a zero-shot relation extraction approach to build knowledge graphs from CGDC archives. We used transformer-based models like DeBERTa, BART, and T5 to identify 20 relation types from Wikidata, offering a method to improve the searchability of CGDC archives.</p>
<p>Towards a National Collection programme final conference</p>	<p>20th-21st November 2024</p> <p>Audience - National 375</p>	<p>OHOS PI Lorna Hughes presented the keynote talk 'Lost in the flood: Finding and using CGDC' at the final TaNC Conference in Manchester. The OHOS team also conducted a panel discussion on Community Generated Digital Content.</p>
<p>'AI and Metadata: lessons learned from the AHRC <i>Our Heritage Our Stories</i> Towards a National Collection Project'</p> <p>Second edition of the DiHeLib Conference "(Meta-) Data orchestration: connecting manuscript collections for innovating research - 'Berlinka' in action"</p>	<p>21st-23rd November 2024</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 50</p>	<p>Presentation by OHOS PI Lorna Hughes at the DiHeLib Conference at the Jagiellonian University, Krakow. The talk launched the OHOS project outputs to an international audience.</p>
<p>BEYOND2024: Creative Cities</p>	<p>25th-27th November 2024</p> <p>Audience – International, approx. 150</p>	<p>Lorna Hughes, Hannah Barker and Goran Nenadic took part in a panel about creative industry innovation and OHOS outputs at the BEYOND 2024 conference at the University of Manchester. Youcef Benkhedda and Hanna Schmück showcased the AI pipeline and its outputs, including visualisations.</p>

Research Approach

Research on Our Heritage, Our Stories was distributed across five Labs: AI, Linguistics, Archives, History, and the Observatory. These Labs operated semi-autonomously, with distinct teams and approaches, but with continual and overarching collaboration to deliver the project's key goals and milestones. An integrated approach to project design was used, using methodologies including active research, iterative design, and continuous evaluation. Through these approaches, OHOS sought to harmonise a wide variety of CGDC metadata – describing catalogue data, born-digital content, text, image, moving image, and audio data – from a broad sample of community archives across the UK, to enhance digital search and interoperability and make these resources available to a fresh range of audiences and users. Our Observatory offers these materials to the public, as well as other researchers, through a new and standards-based interface. The design of this Observatory was informed by TNA's expert digital services team, in collaboration with the project Labs and our wide network of partners. A key part of our work was in holistically scoping key questions associated with the integrated delivery of CGDC metadata, including legal, structural, and logistical considerations and incorporating associated research findings about these challenges into our research outputs as well as our future recommendations.

The overall structure of the project was coordinated by the team at the University of Glasgow. For the first phase of the project, project meetings occurred regularly, with weekly meetings that rotated in topic between: a meeting of all investigators for core project planning, discussions, and decision-making; an impact-focused meeting relating to engagement, outreach, and dissemination (principally relating to the Archives and History Labs); an all-hands roundtable for cross-Lab discussions; and a technical delivery meeting for discussing key technical questions (principally relating to the AI, Linguistics, and Observatory Labs). In the second half of the project, once a shared project vision and workplan were in place across Labs, these meetings were replaced with regular progress meetings between each Lab and the project management team, with cross-Lab meetings organised as and when needed to progress. Our project advisory board, chaired by Professor Barry Smith at the University of London, advised on progress and overall strategy, providing operational oversight, acting as a positive feedback loop, and advising on broader applicability of outputs, ensuring value/impact beyond the project.

Archives Lab

The main goals of the Archives Lab were: development of a data and collections strategy for the project, including identification of collections that could be used for our AI Pipeline; scoping CGDC and its ecosystems to develop an understanding of the digital lifecycle and the institutional and organisational frameworks that enables its creation and sustainability in the UK; development of a semantics-aware, FAIR-compliant and sustainable post-custodial model for use across the community archives sector in the UK; and documentation and dissemination of the post-custodial model for CGDC.

This meant that the Archives Lab was the focal point for the project's work with community archives themselves and involved collaborating extensively with community archives on engagement activities and workshops and working closely with them to have their data enriched by the project's NLP pipeline.

The Archives Lab worked actively with all the heritage and collecting organisations involved in the project that create, manage, or disseminate CGDC, as well as the extensive stakeholder community working with this material. When finding and approaching community archives who might contribute data to the project, a conscientious effort was made to try and include a balanced, representative, and comprehensive range of CGDC in the project, since the CGDC available to the team would inform all aspects of project development (including AI, linguistics, and the Observatory design), as well as the diversity of community data made available in new and innovative ways as a final project outcome. To do this, extensive scoping work was undertaken to identify organisations across the UK producing CGDC, with hundreds of community heritage organisations identified and approached by the project. While there were several barriers that prevented some of these scoped organisations from working with the project (discussed further in the Research Results section of this report below, over a hundred community organisations collaborated with the OHOS project in some form before its conclusion (as detailed in the ‘Community Partners’ section of the ‘Partnership Structure’ section of this report). Fourteen organisations were funded through a flexible Community Fund to enable valuable community input into the project, foreground the richness of UK CGDC, and foster innovative grassroots public engagement.

Alongside direct engagement with community organisations on project activities, the Archives Lab simultaneously deployed a mixed methods approach to research and better understand the ecosystem of community content – including its creation and management, its use and reuse, and the ethical and legal frameworks surrounding this content – in close collaboration with heritage organisations and community groups. This involved a variety of data-gathering methods, including interviews, focus groups, workshops, and reviews of existing practice – details of these events can be found in the ‘Events and Consultations’ section of this report. This research formed a building block for the Observatory and AI Lab development and outputs, working to develop these tools in an iterative process with our project partners and our wider network of community archives and archival practitioners. Moreover, this data was central to the Archives Lab undertaking ethical and meaningful co-curation with community archives to generate best practice frameworks and effective training resources which can be embedded into archival education and professional development for working with CGDC. The result of this work is the project’s Post-Custodial Toolkit, a key output developed by the Archives Lab that provides community organisations with the means to effectively manage their own materials, adhering to a post-custodial approach that emphasises the importance of communities maintaining curatorial control over their own resources.

Fig. 1: Example of Archives Lab activities – Barras Hunt for the Being Human Festival.

Source: Nella McNicol.

Fig. 2: Example of Archives Lab activities – Kinloch Historical Society Isle of Lewis workshop October 2024.

Source: Donnie Macleod.

Fig. 3: Kinloch Historical Society Community-Generated Archive. 'S.S City of Karachi 1957 Sydney, Mary and James, Sydney'. Source: Lorna Hughes.

AI Lab and Linguistics Workstream

The AI Lab was the home of the project's AI pipeline, which used Natural Language Processing (NLP) methods to enrich CGDC provided to the project by community organisations, in preparation for the inclusion of this material in the project Observatory. NLP is a sub-area of Computational Linguistics or, more generally, Artificial Intelligence, that concerns the automated and computerised processing and analysis of unstructured textual data at scale. As such, NLP offers a suite of methodologies for the extraction, analysis, linking, preservation, and discoverability of the knowledge contained in CGDC, often in purely textual form, that was previously disconnected from mainstream collections. With NLP forming the principal approach of the project's AI and Linguistics work, OHOS aimed to overcome a barrier that most community content contributors were traditionally faced with when trying to integrate their content into wider datasets: the need to invest time and effort into transforming their collections into formats that conform to existing data capturing mechanisms and models. This approach not only erodes the complexity and heterogeneity of CGDC, thereby undermining its value, but it is also unfeasible in practical terms for many community organisations because they have limited funds, resources, and time available to expend on wrangling data. Instead, OHOS aimed to allow community organisations to submit their collections as they were, relying on the employed AI pipeline to extract and link meaningful and relevant meta-data and connect community collections to similar resources. The final project pipeline accepted data across the three most relevant formats used by community organisations in curating their content: JSON, XML, and CSV.

The NLP pipeline created for the OHOS project worked on information extraction and semantic enrichment, transforming purely textual data contained in the metadata of provided CGDC into Knowledge Graphs (KG), by extracting and disambiguating entities of interest and relations between them. These KGs subsequently enable visualisation and similarity-based search possibilities on this enriched content, extending how CGDC can be explored and discovered, and facilitating more advanced analysis of this data. Transforming purely textual collections into linked Knowledge Graphs requires several stages of processing: first, central entities in the content are identified (Named Entity Recognition, NER); next, these entities are linked to public knowledge bases, thus effectively disambiguating them from other possible entities (Entity Linking); finally, any relations between these extracted entities are inferred (Relation Extraction). Five entity types were

identified as relevant to CGDC – *Person, Organisation, Location, Date* and *Miscellaneous* – with the AI pipeline performing NER to extract entities of these types from CGDC metadata using the pre-trained transformer language model *BART*. At the Entity Linking stage, these extracted entities were then linked to their equivalent entities in Wikidata, enabling all CGDC processed by the AI pipeline to be connected to one shared knowledge base that is widely used in Linked Open Data approaches, facilitating maximal interoperability with other content.

Likewise, Wikidata was used as the basis for Relation Extraction, with twenty relations from Wikidata’s relations set identified as key to CGDC, shown in Table 1 below. Relations link two entities: head entity and tail entity (e.g. a Person (head entity) is connected to an Organisation (tail entity)). The relation extraction process was supported by use of a manually annotated dataset, whereby members of the OHOS team labelled a dataset of CGDC textual metadata with relationships between named entities, to evaluate performance between human readers and transformer-based Relation Extraction models. To conduct Relation Extraction, two sentences were provided to a model as input – a *premise* and a *hypothesis* – with the model testing the similarity between the two. An input sentence from the contributed CGDC data was considered to be the *premise*, while a *hypothesis* was automatically generated by populating a sentence template (predefined for a particular relation type) with input entities. The premise-hypothesis pair was then presented to the model: if the model detected entailment – that is, if the automatically-generated *hypothesis* sentence could be considered true based on the input *premise* sentence – then the relationship being tested between the input entities (corresponding to the template) was considered to be accurate.

Table 1: The relation types relevant to CGDC, their equivalent human-readable label, their Wikidata identifiers (linked to a page with their definitions and synonyms) and the types of head and tail entities involved.

Wikidata Property/ Relation Type	Human-readable Label	Wikidata ID	Head Entity Type	Tail Type Entity
affiliation	connected to	P1416	Person	Organisation
			Organisation	Organisation
date_of_birth	born on	P569	Person	Date
date_of_death	died on	P570	Person	Date
depicts	shows	P180	Miscellaneous	Person
			Miscellaneous	Location
			Miscellaneous	Organisation
			Miscellaneous	Miscellaneous
employer	worked for	P108	Person	Person
			Person	Organisation
inception	began to exist on	P571	Organisation	Date
			Location	Date
			Miscellaneous	Date
location	happened in	P276	Miscellaneous	Location
located_in	located in	P706	Location	Location
member_of	member of	P463	Person	Organisation
notable_work	created or built	P800	Person	Miscellaneous
			Organisation	Miscellaneous

			Person	Location
occupation	worked as	P106	Person	Miscellaneous
operating_area	operated in	P2541	Miscellaneous	Location
participant_in	participated in	P1344	Person	Miscellaneous
			Organisation	Miscellaneous
partnership_with	collaborated with	P2652	Organisation	Organisation
place_of_birth	born in	P19	Person	Location
point_in_time	happened on or as of	P585	Miscellaneous	Date
			Location	Date
residence	lived in	P551	Person	Location
significant_person	wrote to, spoke to or met	P3342	Person	Person
spouse	married to	P26	Person	Person
work_location	worked in	P937	Person	Location
			Organisation	Location

In Table 2 below, we provide examples of premise-hypothesis pairs, in which the hypothesis was generated based on a template. Using this approach, relationships between the Named Entities in a given item of CGDC can then be automatically extracted and labelled to build a Knowledge Graph of the underlying data. Drawing on the linguistics expertise present in the project team, the AI Lab and Linguistics workstream also explored the use of linguistic resources for improving the performance of these large language models. Specifically, the team experimented with integrating the Historical Thesaurus of English (HT) into the relation extraction process, using the HT as a comprehensive source of synonyms for the predicates within the template sentences of each relation type. Using this approach, additional hypothesis sentences could then be generated for each relation type, by which to test whether a particular generated relationship between entities was accurate. The AI lab also explored existing transformer-based language models (DeBERTa, BART, and T5) for a ‘zero-shot’ approach to relation extraction, as well as an ‘Ensemble model’ to combine outcomes of relation extraction from different approaches.

Table 2: Examples of premise-hypothesis pairs used as inputs to the NLI models.

Relation Type	Template	Premise (Input Sentence with Entities underlined)	Template-generated hypothesis
inception	<Org Loc Misc> was created on <Date>	Operating from <u>1923</u> , the <u>Lady Magdalen</u> was just one of the ferries that would carry passengers and cars across the Cleddau River.	Lady Magdalen was created on 1923.
operating_area	<Misc> operated in <Loc>	Operating from 1923, the <u>Lady Magdalen</u> was just one of the ferries that would carry passengers and cars across the <u>Cleddau River</u> .	Lady Magdalen operated in Cleddau River.

The combination of extracted, disambiguated entities, their canonical identifiers, and extracted normalised relations, allowed the underlying data - CGDC, in the case of OHOS - to be transformed into corresponding, interlinked Knowledge Graphs. In this way, Knowledge Graphs offer a way of finding and discovering explicitly similar items – that is, materials that mention the same entities. In OHOS, these Knowledge Graphs facilitate the discoverability and analysis of contributed CGDC through the project’s Observatory, by allowing querying of its content. Furthermore though, the identification of common entities and relations across different sources will automatically link together previously disconnected collections, which will facilitate their exploration and discovery; for example, a user initially interested in one specific collection might be recommended similar items from different collections that are also of interest, due to entities identified in their descriptions being related in the underlying Knowledge Graph. These can be further complimented by automated methods that enable items from different collections that mention the same entities to be automatically linked, or materials to be linked other items of interest with similar semantic content – i.e. those that pertain to similar topics without explicitly mentioning the same entity. The pipeline processes therefore made disparate and diverse CGDC FAIR through the Observatory: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

While the state-of-the-art NLP approaches described above have been applied to various subject areas prior to the OHOS project, they had not been widely employed in the general context of digital archives or, more specifically, to the preservation of CGDC. With NLP tools typically trained on extremely large datasets, the smaller datasets of CGDC collections and the diversity of language contained within them (often incorporating regional and social language varieties) posed a challenge, with the AI Lab and Linguistics workstream also involved in research around CGDC as a unique discourse type. This work on language and dialect within a community archival setting enabled us to engage more fully with the complexity of CGDC data and metadata as it appears in discourse communities and consider how generic methods might be adapted to more appropriately and comprehensively capture the context-dependent richness of CGDC. Furthermore, all information extraction tasks, such as the proposed semantic enrichment of CGDC, mandate a careful balance between precision (among the produced extractions, how many are correct?) and recall (among all true extractions, how many were produced?). Different considerations regarding this trade-off apply, depending on the eventual applications of this extracted information. For example, a historian might only be interested in items linked to specific date ranges that were recovered with high precision. Conversely, an enthusiast might want to recover all possible connections to their item of interest, such as their hometown, even if some of these turn out to be irrelevant. Balancing this intricate interplay, the OHOS AI pipeline and Observatory interface researched a range of different bespoke use cases in their development, so as to enable the underlying CGDC to be used effectively by as wide a range of audiences as possible.

Observatory Lab

Once CGDC provided by partner archives who had agreed that it could be processed by the project was enriched via the AI pipeline, it was sent to the Observatory Lab at The National Archives for publication within the project’s public-facing Observatory. In the first eighteen months of the project, the Observatory Lab’s overarching approach was to iteratively and concurrently deliver prototypes that would lead to the development of the final project Observatory for the public to view, analyse, and compare CGDC, and reuse this data via the project’s Remixer Suite. The prototypes were: existing content management system-based (Prototype 1); bespoke (2-dimensional) (Prototype 2); and experimental (3-dimensional) (Prototype 3). Initially, these prototypes were aimed at addressing casual and community users, with browse, search, and annotation

tools for users to explore CGDC. The Observatory initially followed an agile approach to development at this time, whereby three Research Software Engineers (RSEs) worked in time-bounded iterations (sprints) to deliver a set amount of work (stories). The agile approach was felt to assist with frequent delivery and feedback opportunities, and the ability to shift activities depending on the outcome of research and user engagement activities. During this period, the Observatory Lab also undertook research into the existing landscape surrounding CGDC and linked data approaches, analysing interfaces based on linked data both within and outside the cultural heritage sector for the development of the Observatory and Remixer Suite. This included analysing existing use of timelines, maps, and annotations tools, and user research to understand potential users. Research activities also followed the agile approach, defining research questions to be answered during a sprint, using story point estimation (an estimate of the complexity of a piece of work) to guide the required depth of the research. In addition to literature reviews and analysis of practice, engagement surveys and co-design workshops were planned to target potential user groups (e.g. community archive groups and academic researchers) to assist with gathering requirements and design tools to meet their needs.

Following the first eighteen months of development of the Observatory, a shift in delivery model took place, with the development of the Observatory moving to TNA's Digital Services Team and drawing on their ongoing work and expertise developing the next iteration of TNA's Discovery platform. This meant that, rather than attempting to produce an entirely new, bespoke interface and platform for the project, the OHOS Observatory could be developed according to principles and technologies already in use at TNA, rapidly reducing development time and ensuring maximal compatibility with the Discovery platform. The Observatory is therefore based on a range of industry-tested technologies and standards, applied to the new context of CGDC, with the figure below demonstrating the final data flow of CGDC on the project. User testing was carried out working with the archives that contributed data to the project for research. The project is therefore a powerful exemplar of the utilisation of existing infrastructure as a component of a national collection, which was also a key consideration in developing robust approaches to data sharing and GDPR across institution types (IROs and HEIs) with different legal bases for processing data for research, and for re-publishing data in the OHOS Observatory.

Fig. 4: Final data flow of CGDC on the project.

History Lab

The History Lab's primary focus was on the use and significance of CGDC beyond the project, and specifically for history research, emphasising the wider importance of these materials and the impact of their increased accessibility and use. Core to this was the exploration of key research questions for a series of research studies: these studies show the value of CGDC for research across multiple disciplines, engaging academic, community, and family researchers in the use and potential of discoverable and linked CGDC, including generating crucial links between the creators and potential end-users of newly opened up CGDC. These studies centred on people, periods, and movements including the postmemory of the Second World War; British popular music heritage; disability rights; and Black and Asian stories of political resistance and cultural identity. These studies revealed compelling new narratives about the histories and development of contemporary British society and showcase the capacity for CGDC to promote marginalised or underrepresented voices and stories.

The History Lab also collaborated closely with the Archives Lab to develop the project's community engagement approaches and its research into the ecosystem of CGDC, allowing the project to work with diverse stakeholder communities with different priorities, interests and needs. This work supported the project in better understanding the wealth of CGDC held within communities and how communities use, or would like to use, this material. A report written in collaboration with *Manchester Histories*, exploring the nature of community archives and the preservation and management of community-generated digital content through a series of interviews with community archives, was a key output of this research (discussed further in this report's 'Research Results' section). As with the Archives Lab, the History Lab's research carefully considered hierarchies and power dynamics, and issues of ethics and legal contexts of CGDC, contributing to the development of the project's post-custodial framework for curating and engaging with community-generated digital content in a collaborative, sustainable, and ethical manner.

Research Results

The Our Heritage, Our Stories project represents the most comprehensive exploration of UK Community-Generated Digital Content (and its position within the wider UK heritage landscape) conducted to date, spanning over three years, incorporating the research of more than twenty academics/researchers, and including collaborations and insights from over a hundred unique community organisations. Consequently, this project's results are extremely wide-ranging and comprise a broad set of outputs and forms. To synthesise this diversity of knowledge, the results below distil the project's research findings around four key themes: the nature of CGDC and its associated practices; new approaches to data linking developed by the project and the position of CGDC within data linking approaches; use and reuse of CGDC facilitated by the project and its use cases; and post-custodial approaches to archival management.

Community-Generated Digital Content

Central to the aims of the project was developing a better understanding of the nature of community-generated digital content (CGDC), as a historically under-appreciated and under-researched form of heritage. This meant exploring the qualities of CGDC as a unique data type, the practices of community organisations in collecting and curating such materials and the lifecycle of such materials, and the status of community organisations and CGDC within the wider heritage sector.

Community-generated digital content (CGDC) is born-digital or digitised content created and/or collected by and/or for a community, which can be held solely online or alongside physical ephemera. It is principally concerned with people and the ways in which they choose to remember their lives, experiences, and histories through digital media. CGDC collections provide communities with agency over their own materials, allowing them to share their stories in their own voices and providing a platform for more authentic representation. CGDC collections are also often formed by communities in response to perceived absences or shortcomings in existing heritage materials: CGDC is frequently produced to preserve aspects of community history that are not preserved elsewhere. As such, this content can serve as a valuable repository of cultural heritage not contained in any other institution or location, encompassing the stories, traditions, and histories of diverse communities and localities beyond those contained in mainstream narratives and institutional collections. CGDC consequently represents a vital resource within the UK cultural heritage landscape, with its preservation and promotion enabling a diversified and democratised national collection.

While this final definition of CGDC arrived at by the project provides a clear view of its nature and utility, it also masks a highly complex, delicate, and diverse ecosystem of at-risk heritage data. OHOS found that the scale and scope of CGDC collections varied widely. Some were highly specific, pertaining to a small number of individuals, such as a family, whereas others centred on world events and incorporated a world-wide network of contributors as their community. CGDC was also found to adopt a highly heterogeneous array of file formats and data types – both in terms of original evidence and in relation to content created as a result of community activity (publications, merchandise etc.) – with these formats and types tailored to the specific requirements of the community producing, maintaining, and using the materials. This, in turn, speaks to the diversity of those who manage CGDC. These can be local groups/businesses/families/archives who are involved in the represented community, individuals distinct from the community but with a specified interest and skillset (for instance web design), or anything in between. Still others are formal heritage institutions who have ingested CGDC as a part of their collections, perhaps out of fear of

loss or perhaps as a part of a funded project or other outreach activity. This plurality of CGDC holders also feeds into a plurality of practices, with OHOS finding that CGDC holders often have very different philosophies, methods, and resources for curating community materials (discussed further in the 'Post-custodial model' section below).

Integrating this wide range of materials and communities into an interoperable, interconnected network not only posed significant technical challenges (discussed further in 'Data Linking' and 'Data use and reuse' sections below) but was also affected by substantial social and systemic factors. A key finding from the project's collaborations with community archives was the extent to which resourcing concerns constrained their activities. Lack of funding was one of the most consistent concerns for the creation of CGDC, emerging as a central theme across interviews and consultations. As well as sustained limitations on funding (a condition felt across the heritage sector but particularly keenly by community organisations operating on much smaller budgets), funding sources for community heritage organisations are also inconsistent, making forward planning much harder and potentially pushing organisations into producing outputs that are valued by funders, rather than those valued by their community.

The almost universally lamented lack of funding is also seen as evidence for more ephemeral considerations, such as the confidence of CGDC creators/holders in the value of their work and their willingness to trust and work with established institutions that may have previously ignored their contributions.

This renders CGDC collections highly delicate, with a high risk of materials being lost if holding organisations are unable to obtain sustained funding: in our series of semi-structured interviews with CGDC holders in the UK (P1), only half of the respondents were found to have, or have had, paid staff working on their teams. In the case of posts that have been secured, employees on community projects are part of very small (sometimes single person) teams and so require a highly diversified skillset to accomplish the needs of the project, sometimes leading to individuals taking on jobs outside of their expertise and training. A second order effect of funding issues is therefore the loss of the labour, skill, and expertise of volunteers within the community heritage sector, which are difficult to replace, and which further increase the fragility of CGDC if institutional/organisational knowledge is lost.

Lack of staffing, funding, specialist digital skills, and the project-based nature of many digital initiatives, means that CGDC remains fragile, largely under-preserved, unlinked, and at risk of loss when exploring the sustainability and practicability of current approaches. The placing of CGDC on the DPC's Global 'Bit List' of Endangered Digital Species reinforces these challenges (<https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/champion-digital-preservation/bit-list>).

Despite the availability of extant guidelines for creating and preserving CGDC (created by, for example, NLHF and other organisations), OHOS identified a need for urgent guidance and, at points, intervention in order to mitigate the threat of irreparable loss (Digital Preservation Coalition, 2024; see also OHOS White paper 1). The inevitable question then arises of: how can we marry the depth, heart, and community value of CGDC content with the conventions and policies of information professionals in a way that does not dilute the uniqueness of CGDC but supports its longevity?

When collaborating with community organisations on the OHOS project, another emergent theme was the saliency of trust within the CGDC ecosystem. While community organisations were often open to collaborating and being part of a larger archival network, they were also keen to maintain their autonomy and individuality, preserving the unique characteristics and user experiences that their collections provide to their communities. Some expressed concerns about the potential consequences of their materials appearing on larger platforms, worrying that if their materials were widely available elsewhere, it might lead to reduced traffic on their own websites, potentially affecting their sustainability and visibility. These challenges are unique to the CGDC ecosystem within the heritage sector and drove the project's development of a post-custodial model that can facilitate community control and empowerment, whilst also enabling its broader integration and sustainment (discussed further below).

Other findings related to rights management and GDPR. All CGDC materials are potentially protected by copyright, and while seeking permission from the copyright holder is the best course of action when in doubt, there are exceptions that allow the use of copyrighted material for research and educational purposes under specific conditions. Creative Commons licenses, while helpful, also impose certain restrictions, such as the share-alike license, which requires any derivative work to also be freely available. Researchers should be cautious when working with CGDC, as they cannot always assume that a website has the right to apply such licenses to material that might belong to someone else. Data protection laws, particularly the Data Protection Act 2018 (which implements the General Data Protection Regulation in the UK), also play a critical role in how personal data is handled in research. Researchers are considered 'data handlers' and must have a legal basis for processing personal data, whether that is through the consent of the data subject or exemptions based on purposes such as archiving or scientific research. Researchers must document their decisions and ensure compliance with these laws, carefully considering the implications of processing personal data. We found that while there was a generally good awareness of rights management, and an awareness of where to go for advice, there was a lack of support for organisations working with data where GDPR was an issue.

Metadata supports every technical aspect of any project involving CGDC, and yet it is one of the most difficult, technical, and unengaging of CGDC creators' tasks. A conclusion from the archives lab research is that everything is a metadata problem: if you can get that right, anything is possible. However, there is very little support for cataloguing and descriptive work in community archives: there is a need for more open training and documentation guidelines for this fundamental task, and for advocacy at the sector level about good data practices and the adoption of standards to support the discovery, management and preservation of CGDC.

Our project used AI and the creation of customised schema to solve the problem of missing and messy metadata through harmonisation of data via our AI pipeline, and solutions such as mapping between different metadata using the layered approach developed by the OHOS AI Lab can integrate non-standard metadata. Solutions of this type have an important role to play innovation in archival management. However, good practice in developing metadata also supports future data aggregation: the more standardised metadata is, with individual metadata fields being used in uniform ways, the more effectively and efficiently it can be aggregated at scale. Better quality data also requires less data cleaning and standardisation at the aggregation stage and is more useful and comprehensible to the end user, and the adoption of archival descriptive standards by community archives that are consistent with community accepted best practice, rather than the creation of idiosyncratic or locally adapted schema, can support discovery and subsequent data aggregation. The adoption of best practice for cataloguing has the key benefit of enabling the sharing of catalogue data beyond the scope of a primary audience and making the data more immediately linkable and discoverable, achieving the sort of goals that were central to OHOS and supporting future harmonisation.

Cataloguing and metadata guidance for community archives is already available, but could usefully be complemented by specific guidance on the creation of metadata and datasets with a view to data aggregation, such as:

- the adoption of a consistent approach,
- the use of machine-readable data, especially for date fields, over data that is only intelligible to a human reader,
- and the repetition of key information at the item level.

Our project used AI approaches to address these structural issues: to harmonise and aggregate disparate metadata, and our solutions are discussed below.

Key Related Outputs

- **P1:** Saving UK CGDC at Risk
- **P4:** Post-Custodial Archival Management
- **D5:** CGDC research studies

Data Linking

The OHOS Observatory sought to link and make more discoverable CGDC. To this end, seven participating community archives provided metadata describing collections ranging from a dozen to over 150,000 records. Data aggregation, data protection and rights-holding considerations highlighted the challenges of working with disparate datasets coming from different sources and created using varied technologies and practices. Many of the challenges associated with data aggregation can technically be overcome but are resource (cost and labour) intensive to address and require specialist skills and knowledge. Further challenges relating to data protection and rights management can also limit technical approaches to data aggregation from what is technically possible to what is permissible. However, despite these challenges, the OHOS project's work successfully demonstrated the rich potential of linking these datasets, provided a viable means of doing so to develop a people's national collection, and showcased how technology and artificial intelligence could further enrich these areas.

The project's AI pipeline provides a functional automated system for the enrichment of CGDC, adapting generic NLP models to the specific context of community materials. This system enables Named Entity Recognition, Entity Linking, and Relation Extraction on CGDC, in the manner outlined in the 'Research Approaches' section above. During the AI Lab's research, metadata in CGDC collections was found to often feature non-standard text, such as short descriptions, misspellings, and obsolete terms, which poses a challenge for entity recognition and linking. Many entities in CGDC metadata also do not have corresponding entries in Wikidata (inherent to their nature as under-represented materials), making entity linking a further challenge and meaning models must classify such entities as "unlinkable" (NIL). These traits make it harder for language models to perform accurately when applied to CGDC compared to well-structured texts like news articles. When evaluating state-of-the-art, general-domain entity linking models, the AI lab found that mGENRE provided the best performance for application to CGDC (ahead of BLINK and EPGEL) because of its superior ability to identify NIL entities, which are common in community archival materials. By utilising this model in conjunction with canonical entities contained in Wikidata, the AI pipeline was able to produce a method for harmonizing different names or terms referring to the same entity across collections.

The AI lab also then developed an automated means of linking these entities into relationships within text, enabling data to be explored through searching for specific relationships. Utilising existing transformer-based language models (DeBERTa, BART, and T5), the team developed a 'zero-shot' approach to relation extraction (described in the 'Research Approaches' section above) that combined these existing models into an 'Ensemble model' which was able to infer relationships between entities (F1-score of 0.487) at a level close to human inter-annotator agreement (F1-score of 0.49). The team also found that this model was able to identify some relationships that were not detected by human annotators but were implicit in the data, suggesting a potential further use for these models to suggest relationships for human verification. When also combined with the knowledge and expertise of community groups holding materials to correct erroneous links and relations, this pipeline enables the creation of a Knowledge Graph with cross-collection

search capabilities, opening up CGDC for connection with other resources, such as provided by the project Observatory.

In constructing the project Observatory, one of the most prominent issues was the inconsistency in metadata across participating archives. Each community archive used unique methods, standards, and terminologies, leading to varied and sometimes ambiguous metadata fields. For example, date fields often had inconsistent formats or meanings—sometimes referring to the creation date of an item, other times to its digitisation or acquisition, or to the dates it covered. Addressing these discrepancies required extensive preprocessing and metadata standardization. This step was crucial because, without harmonised data, automated linking and querying systems would struggle to generate meaningful results. To manage this variability, the OHOS team developed a flexible data model based on common metadata properties identified across the first five datasets. This model initially captured 23 core fields, but as more datasets were ingested, the need for adjustments and expansions became apparent. To develop the core OHOS Data Model, datasets from five community archives were ingested into CIIM and analysed to identify common fields. The primary focus was to standardise key fields, such as creator and provenance, to ensure consistency. These six datasets had from 15 to 52 metadata fields; the three datasets with fewer fields aligned to a standardised structure (Dublin Core, ISAD(G)), with the remaining two datasets with a larger number of fields being custom developed admin/web style data. All fields were modelled to create a superset of 52 distinct fields. From this superset we selected a core set of 23 fields which would form the OHOS Data Model. The selection or exclusion of metadata fields was based on their ability to be made searchable and linkable, prioritising the inclusion of fields that were commonly found across and within multiple datasets. When subsequent datasets were ingested, any additional fields unique to the dataset which were either essential to adequately represent the data, or usefully extended the data model, such as 'language', were added to the OHOS Data Model. With experience, increased knowledge of CGDC, and confidence in the robustness of the OHOS Data Model, we became increasingly confident in excluding data points as it became apparent that many were not widely used across more than one community archive, or not consistently or widely used within a given community archive.

Alongside this, automated enrichment by the AI pipeline added another layer of structure by identifying key entities such as people, places, and events. These steps underscored the importance of maintaining flexibility in automated systems, as metadata schemas must evolve to accommodate the diversity of CGDC. The aggregation process culminated in the creation of a Knowledge Graph, where entities and their relationships were structured and stored using Elasticsearch. This enabled users to explore connections between archives in ways that had not been possible before. For example, metadata from one archive could now be semantically linked to related data in another, facilitating a richer understanding of historical or cultural narratives. This approach demonstrated the potential of Knowledge Graphs to unify disparate datasets while preserving the unique context of each contributing archive. With the caveat that community collaboration and control of their materials must remain at the heart of the CGDC ecosystem, future tools could go even further. With the integration of generative AI, metadata gaps might be filled automatically, and relationships between items could be inferred or enriched with additional context. For example, an AI-powered system could suggest links between a historical photograph and a related text entry in another archive, creating new opportunities for discovery.

Despite these advancements, the inclusion of personal and sensitive data posed significant challenges. A substantial portion of CGDC metadata contained names, addresses, and other identifying information, some of which fell under GDPR's definition of special category data. Nearly 60% of CGDC metadata processed by

the project contains identifiable personal details, such as the names of creators, and a smaller portion includes sensitive data, like information about ethnicity or health. This raises significant challenges under GDPR, necessitating additional layers of oversight, including a comprehensive Data Protection Impact Assessment and the establishment of takedown procedures to handle privacy concerns. While AI tools could identify standardised forms of personal data, they were less effective with the nuanced and varied data found in CGDC. As a result, much of the data processing had to be performed manually to ensure compliance. This highlighted a need for more sophisticated AI tools that can detect and handle personal data in diverse and non-standard formats, particularly relevant in the context of CGDC. Scaling the project also revealed challenges. Aggregating more datasets amplified the complexity of metadata standardization and processing. Each new archive introduced unique nuances, increasing the workload and resource requirements. This growth underscored the importance of scalable systems that could adapt to incremental changes while maintaining consistency across datasets. One strategy proposed for scaling involved setting minimal metadata requirements, such as titles, descriptions, and dates, allowing archives to participate without extensive preprocessing. This approach could make aggregation more inclusive while still enabling basic linking and discovery.

The OHOS project's research highlighted the transformative potential of automated tools in managing and linking CGDC. By leveraging advanced natural language processing and machine learning, the project's AI pipeline and Observatory can enrich metadata and uncover hidden connections between datasets. Semantic linking through Knowledge Graphs opens up new possibilities for exploring relationships across archives, offering users deeper insights into cultural heritage. At the same time, our findings have underscored the importance of privacy-first design, with it being imperative that automated systems integrate tools to identify and manage personal data, ensuring compliance with regulations like GDPR. As archives increasingly contribute data from the 20th and 21st centuries, addressing these privacy concerns will be crucial to maintaining trust and inclusivity. Ultimately, OHOS has demonstrated that, while challenges remain, automated processing and linking hold immense promise for CGDC: by combining flexibility, AI-driven enrichment, and robust privacy safeguards, these systems can unlock the potential of community archives, making their rich and diverse histories accessible to all.

Key Related Outputs

- **D1:** AI pipeline
- **D2:** Observatory
- **D4:** Prototype approaches to semantic crosswalks
- **P2:** Metadata crosswalks beyond Discovery
- **P3:** Emerging Approaches to Data Aggregation and Rights

Data Use and Reuse

As the findings above show, idiosyncrasies of CGDC metadata present both a rich resource and a complex one: each archive operates with its own conventions, creating bespoke fields, and using different terminology to represent unique histories and communities. Yet, the potential of CGDC also lies in its transformation into something greater. Through enrichment processes like Named Entity Recognition (NER), individual metadata records were linked to broader datasets such as Wikidata, creating a dynamic network

of information. This approach turned disconnected archives into a cohesive Knowledge Graph, allowing users to explore relationships between people, locations, and organizations across collections, from across the UK. These linked datasets have then been made even more accessible through the Observatory's 'Remixer Suite', enabling users to query, filter, and combine metadata from various sources.

The Remixer Suite demonstrates the potential of CGDC aggregation when paired with advanced technology. Designed as a user-facing platform, the Remixer Suite provides a dynamic interface where users can explore, query, and combine metadata from multiple community archives in novel ways. Its underlying architecture leverages Elasticsearch and GraphQL, enabling swift, flexible access to the aggregated data while allowing for real-time filtering and transformation of queries. A central strength of the Remixer Suite lies in its ability to make sense of the complexity inherent in CGDC metadata. By harmonising diverse datasets, the suite creates a uniform framework that allows users to interact with what would otherwise be fragmented and inconsistent records. For instance, while each community archive may describe similar content in different ways—some labelling items as “photographs” and others as “images” or “snapshots”—the Remixer Suite's architecture maps these variations into a consistent schema. This enables users to search seamlessly across archives, filtering items based on shared attributes such as date ranges, locations, or creators.

Throughout the project, the OHOS team was mindful of the diversity of users who might wish to use and reuse CGDC, with development of the Observatory designed to accommodate this broad spectrum of users and uses. As such, the suite is well-suited for researchers, educators, and cultural enthusiasts who wish to delve into the interconnected narratives hidden within CGDC. Users can create custom searches to explore specific themes or stories, such as tracing the history of a local landmark or mapping the contributions of a particular community to a cultural movement. With features that support dynamic filtering, users can refine their queries iteratively – starting broad and then narrowing down by adding parameters like date, place, or related individuals. For example, a researcher could begin with a simple query for “industrial heritage in Wales” and gradually refine it by focusing on contributions by women in the 19th century, ultimately building a dataset that highlights previously underrepresented stories. The Remixer Suite makes it possible to layer these searches, drawing metadata from multiple archives into a single view.

Another transformative feature of the Remixer Suite is its potential for data visualization. Once metadata is aggregated and queried, users can generate interactive outputs such as timelines, maps, or a ‘tag view’ of entities in the data. A timeline might chart the evolution of a local festival across decades, while a map could visualise the geographical spread of items from a specific community. These visual tools offer users new ways to contextualise and interpret metadata, bringing to life the stories embedded in the archives. To address the inherent challenge of presenting items outside their original contexts, the Remixer Suite incorporates design elements aimed at providing just enough background to guide users. Each metadata record in the suite links directly to its source archive, ensuring that users can easily follow up for more in-depth exploration. However, presenting items with sufficient context remains a delicate balance. Without duplicating the original archive's website, the suite must present records in a way that avoids misinterpretation or loss of meaning.

The suite's flexible design positions it as a scalable solution for CGDC aggregation. As more archives contribute data, the suite can accommodate expanding datasets while maintaining a coherent user experience. However, this scalability also introduces challenges. Too much standardisation risks erasing the cultural specificity that makes CGDC valuable, while too little undermines usability and interoperability. Ensuring consistency in data presentation and query functionality across a growing number of archives will require ongoing refinement of the suite's architecture. Future iterations of the Remixer Suite could integrate

generative AI to enhance its capabilities further. AI tools could help suggest related records, identify gaps in metadata, or provide automated summaries of complex collections. Additionally, the integration of semantic search capabilities would allow users to query the data more intuitively, exploring connections and themes that might not be explicitly tagged in the metadata. By enabling dynamic exploration and visualisation, the Remixer Suite transforms how users engage with community-driven cultural heritage, making it not just accessible but also interactive and inspiring. As it evolves, the suite has the potential to redefine how we interact with and reinterpret the past.

The significance for research of facilitating greater use and reuse of CGDC cannot be understated, as demonstrated by the History Lab's series of use cases. For example, CGDC was found to play a pivotal role in preserving and analysing the evolving memory of the Second World War, offering unique insights into how this history is transmitted across generations (<https://zenodo.org/records/11244081>). CGDC archives, such as *The Russian Arctic Convoy Museum*, the *International Bomber Command Centre digital archive*, and *The Women's Land Army and Timber Corps* website, allow descendants to share stories, photographs, and personal insights about their relatives' wartime experiences. This creates a repository of familial and individual memory that bridges personal history with broader social narratives, fostering intergenerational dialogue: family members inspired by research or interviews often reconnect with their relatives' experiences, blending personal discovery with collective memory. CGDC also highlights underrepresented perspectives, such as those of Caribbean RAF servicemen whose wartime contributions intertwine with broader migration and post-war stories. This broadens the scope of our understanding of Second World War memory, showing how CGDC can provide invaluable resources to understand how memory evolves and adapts across generations and cultural contexts, particularly as the war shifts from living memory to post-memory. Community digital collections thus act as both public memorials and research archives, democratising access to these stories and enabling broader participation in memory-making.

CGDC was also found to be crucial for uncovering and broadening the history of grassroots music-making and consumption, particularly in late 20th-century Britain (<https://zenodo.org/records/11262741>). Traditional narratives often prioritise famous musicians, iconic scenes, and predominantly white, male contributions, leaving significant historical gaps that CGDC helps to fill by offering firsthand accounts, memorabilia, images and oral histories documenting less-celebrated music scenes, minority contributions, and regional activities. CGDC showcases widespread but under-documented amateur music-making, emphasising its role in everyday life across genres and regions: for example, sites such as *Played in a Band* document the vibrant music scenes in cities like Nottingham, challenging the dominant focus on major hubs such as London or Liverpool. Projects such as the *Manchester Digital Music Archive* also allow CGDC to highlight the contributions of women, LGBTQ+, and Black musicians. These materials reveal how local and global influences intersected to create syncretic music scenes, such as Manchester's reggae-inspired genres that shaped the city's global reputation. CGDC enables communities to document their histories independently, offering narratives that challenge mainstream depictions. For example, the *Acid House Flashback* site reframes Blackburn's 1980s rave scene as a grassroots rebellion against socio-economic decline, while also showcasing the joy, creativity, and unity of participants. These factors mean CGDC provides a rich resource for exploring themes such as identity, community formation, and social networks, as well as the interplay of class, race, gender and geography within music scenes.

CGDC similarly enables a more comprehensive view of disability rights history, particularly in the later 20th century (<https://zenodo.org/records/11262819>). While traditional archival sources often focus on institutional processes and government records, CGDC—especially when created by individuals involved in

activism—provides a more personal, nuanced, and grassroots perspective. This shift in sources enriches the historical understanding of the disability rights movement, revealing not just the outcomes of major national legislation, but also the intricate, everyday struggles of individuals and communities. By supplementing ‘traditional’ institutional archives with material produced by the disabled community and advocacy groups, CGDC provides a more nuanced perspective on the disability rights movement, whilst also emphasising the diversity of views within the movement. Not all activists agreed on methods or ideologies, and the oral histories found on CGDC sites reveal tensions between different approaches to advocacy. This disagreement over strategy is critical in understanding the movement’s internal diversity and the different personal and philosophical motivations driving its participants. By documenting personal experiences in oral histories, CGDC also provides a richer and more detailed account of the intersection between disability and everyday life, showing that the struggle for rights was not limited to political battles but also extended to the lived realities of people with disabilities.

The critical role of CGDC in preserving and showcasing narratives of Black and Asian Britons, particularly in relation to experiences of racism and activism during the late 20th century, was also uncovered during the OHOS project’s research (<https://zenodo.org/records/11262957>). CGDC initiatives such as the *Swadhinata Trust*, *Tandana archives*, and projects such as *African Stories in Hull and East Yorkshire* and *Where Are You Really From?* serve as digital repositories for oral histories, political ephemera, and autobiographical narratives. These CGDC archives address the historical exclusion of Black and Asian voices in mainstream narratives by documenting their cultural, social, and political experiences, particularly their responses to racism. The stories recorded on the *Swadhinata Trust* and *Tandana* sites describe activism on the part of second-generation British Asians during the 1970s and 1980s, and show a route through which ‘composure’, in the form of a psychically satisfying autobiographical narrative, can be achieved through collective stories about resistance. These community archives not only preserve history but also act as tools for ongoing advocacy, reflection, and community building, and by empowering communities to shape their own historical narratives, agency and ‘composure’ are enabled for these groups.

These use cases demonstrate the power of CGDC and the importance of facilitating its use and reuse. However, as indicated elsewhere, this does not come without its challenges, not least in the field of ethics and rights issues. Because CGDC materials are often curated and shared by individuals or groups who may not follow the same standards as academic and archival professionals, researchers need to approach these resources with care, making sure their use aligns with legal, ethical, and institutional frameworks. The History Lab also explored legal and ethical considerations when using CGDC for research, developing several key recommendations.

One of the primary considerations is copyright. All CGDC materials are protected by copyright, and while seeking permission from the copyright holder is the best course of action when in doubt, there are exceptions that allow the use of copyrighted material for research and educational purposes under specific conditions. Creative Commons licenses, while helpful, also impose certain restrictions, such as the share-alike license, which requires any derivative work to also be freely available. Researchers should be cautious, as they cannot always assume that a website has the right to apply such licenses to material that might belong to someone else. Data protection laws, particularly the Data Protection Act 2018 (which implements the General Data Protection Regulation in the UK), also play a critical role in how personal data is handled in research. Researchers are considered ‘data handlers’ and must have a legal basis for processing personal data, whether that is through the consent of the data subject or exemptions based on purposes such as

archiving or scientific research. Researchers must document their decisions and ensure compliance with these laws, carefully considering the implications of processing personal data.

Beyond legal obligations, ethical dimensions are crucial when using CGDC. This is discussed in our report, *A free resource for all? Legal and ethical considerations when using CGDC for research* (<https://zenodo.org/records/11262943>). Researchers should reflect on the potential harm and benefits their work may bring, integrating ethical considerations into every stage of the research process. It is vital to engage with stakeholders, particularly those whose work and identities are represented in CGDC, to understand their perspectives and concerns. While it may not always be necessary to seek informed consent for the use of CGDC, researchers should always consider the wishes of the individuals involved in the creation and representation of the content. For university-based researchers, there is an additional layer of responsibility. They must ensure their research adheres to institutional ethical frameworks, which may require formal peer ethical review before using CGDC materials. In this way, the guidance calls for a thoughtful, multifaceted approach to using these valuable resources, balancing legal requirements, ethical considerations, and institutional policies.

Prototype Approaches to Semantic Crosswalks

One tangible avenue for embracing both the richness and complexity of community archives is the creation of dynamic 3D network visualisations (see figure below) that can be explored online. By visualising entities extracted from the OHOS archives and linking those mentioned in the metadata of the same archival item, this approach aims to make collections more tangible, dynamically explorable, and demonstrate the wealth of resources they embody. Building directly on the AI pipeline outputs described in the Data linking section, these visualisations display a diverse range of entity types, including events, organisations, people, works of art, and products.

One of the primary benefits of 3D network visualisations emerges from the ability to provide a clear visual representation of the 'shape' of individual community archives since it is possible to discern types of archives via the colour-coding of different entity types and the connectedness of subparts of the network. Additionally, users have the option to prioritise matters of personal relevance by tracing stories based on shared relations to events, places, and other factors. This personalised approach promotes exploring the context behind the materials by clicking on the item in question as well as related items which redirects to the item in the Observatory, on Wikidata, or in the community archive itself. This has the potential to enable a deeper understanding of the collections and fosters a more meaningful connection to the materials.

In future projects, there is scope for incorporating additional entity and link types into these networks, such as political or religious entities, or those specific to individual archives. Dynamic 3D networks could further illustrate the growth of a community archive over time, revealing new insights about the entities involved through the chronological addition of items. This underscores the potential for ongoing development and enrichment of community archives, demonstrating the transformative power of technology in preserving and connecting valuable cultural and historical resources.

Fig. 25: Snapshot of the 3D network representing the Morrab Archive with one event-type entity highlighted. Courtesy of Hanna Schmück.

Wikibase Instance

Another output of the pipeline data is a Wikibase instance, developed in collaboration with the National Library of Wales.

Wikibase is a free and open-source platform that powers Wikidata, Wikimedia's linked open database of human knowledge. It can function as a standalone database, leveraging many tools developed for Wikidata while offering users complete control over data structure, licensing, and access. Wikibase allows for the creation and management of complex, multilingual RDF Knowledge Graphs through a user-friendly interface and a suite of tools, some of which require technical expertise. Designed for interoperability, the platform can integrate with Wikidata, enabling federated querying and alignment between datasets. The OHOS Wikibase is a preconfigured, cloud-hosted instance of Wikibase, supported by a long-term commitment from the Wikimedia Foundation to provide free hosting and technical assistance. Alternatively, the platform can be hosted locally, offering even greater customisation options.

The benefits of incorporating this platform into the OHOS data pipeline fall into two key categories: access and engagement.

Access

Wikibase provides a sustainable, accessible repository for pipeline data. The AI pipeline is specifically designed to present heritage-related information as linked entities, making Wikibase an ideal platform for hosting such data. Additionally, the pipeline generates Wikidata identifiers for these entities whenever possible, allowing the Wikibase query service to retrieve supplementary information from Wikidata. Wikibase also supports multilingual data storage. For example, the People's Collection Wales dataset contains both English and Welsh data and enables the addition of labels and descriptions for extracted entities in both languages. The OHOS Wikibase is publicly accessible online, allowing anyone to explore or reuse the data freely.

Engagement

Wikibase, like other Wikimedia platforms, is designed to foster collaboration and engagement. The OHOS Wikibase empowers community archives to enhance, refine, and expand their datasets. Administrators can control editing permissions, and changes can be made directly via the interface or through batch-upload tools. This setup enables communities to take ownership of their data while collaboratively shaping its structure and representation. Each archive can make independent decisions about its data while contributing to a cohesive, interconnected dataset.

Moreover, the dataset creates opportunities for further AI enrichment or model retraining using improved data. A notable example is leveraging bilingual data to enhance AI pipelines and named entity recognition (NER) tools for smaller, under-resourced languages.

Key Related Outputs

- **D2:** Observatory
- **D3:** Remixer Suite
- **D5:** CGDC research studies
- **P2:** Metadata crosswalks beyond Discovery
- **P3:** Emerging Approaches to Data Aggregation and Rights

Data Sharing on Research Projects

In addition to findings around the use and reuse of CGDC, the project also made key discoveries around the use of data on research projects more widely and the challenges that projects seeking to engage in substantial cross-institutional collaboration face.

Data sharing agreements were developed across the project. There were challenges in establishing these due to the complexity of the project structure and the variable nature of the data in scope. However, a solution was co-created across the partnership, which can be used as a model for addressing GDPR issues in similar projects in future.

OHOS has used four types of data sharing agreements concerning CGDC, the structure of which is represented in the diagram below:

1. A Permission to Use Metadata Agreement on the CGDC between OHOS and the Community Archives.
2. A Joint Controller Agreement regarding the metadata between the University of Glasgow and The National Archives.
3. A Data Processing Agreement between the University of Glasgow and the University of Manchester.
4. A three-year Permission to Publish Metadata Agreement between OHOS and the Community Archives upon completion of the project.

Fig. 6: Diagram representing the four types of data sharing agreements used.

Post-Custodial Model

The project's engagement with the diverse practices adopted by individual organisations, which have been tailored to the requirements and functions of their materials in their communities, has emphasised the limitations of top-down, one-size-fits-all approaches to custodianship and reinforced the necessity of a model that allows for communities to curate their materials independently and idiosyncratically, while retaining their ability to link with wider resources and standards. Consequently, the project's research has led it to advocate for a post-custodial approach in managing CGDC. This model reimagines traditional archival practices by shifting the balance of control from centralised institutions to the communities that create and understand their heritage. In a post-custodial framework, communities maintain physical and intellectual ownership of their materials while providing digital copies to archives for preservation and broader access. This allows communities to retain agency over their histories, ensuring that their narratives are authentically preserved and accurately represented.

Traditional custodial approaches often marginalise or neglect CGDC, resulting in orphaned content, fragmented records, and isolated archives. The post-custodial model counters this by fostering community-

led documentation practices while connecting them to institutional networks and resources. This collaboration enables sustainable preservation while maintaining the distinctiveness of each community's heritage. The post-custodial model embraces tailored solutions that respect the unique practices of each community, ensuring that their materials remain relevant and accessible. Additionally, the post-custodial approach challenges conventional notions of archival professionalism by recognising the value of community-driven expertise. Grassroots efforts to document and preserve cultural narratives demonstrate innovative methods that redefine the archival field, shifting the "expert voice" from centralised bodies to the creators themselves. This reorientation promotes inclusivity and participation, enriching the historical record.

By promoting partnerships between communities and institutions, the post-custodial model also enhances the visibility and reach of community archives. These connections enable community-generated materials to enter the broader cultural heritage landscape, ensuring that their stories gain the recognition and audience they deserve. Moreover, this approach addresses long-standing historical injustices by decentralising archival power, providing an avenue to document histories that have been overlooked or excluded from mainstream narratives. As a model, the post-custodial approach enables community archives to shift the balance of power in archival preservation, attain greater autonomy, and move away from traditional "custodial" approaches where national libraries and archives define practice (also helping to address issues of trust discussed in the 'Community-Generated Digital Content' section above).

Supporting this effort, the OHOS and DPC '[Digital Preservation Toolkit](#)' provides practical guidance for communities and institutions to implement these practices effectively. This resource emphasises the importance of community involvement in the ongoing care and management of digital heritage, bridging the gap between grassroots efforts and institutional expertise. The toolkit guides users through the basics of archival management in a series of levels, ensuring that communities at all stages of the digital preservation journey are able to find and implement relevant guidance. For those at the very beginning of their digital preservation work, introductory guidance is provided in the 'What is Digital Preservation', 'Explaining the Lifecycle' and 'You are not Alone' documents. A series of topics are then provided to give users a basic digital preservation workflow that can be adapted and added to according to each community's needs. The toolkit also includes a series of case studies to show how community archive groups across the UK are operating, to give community groups both advice and inspiration. A further list of resources gives information on additional guides, processes and standards used across the archives and record keeping sector.

Key Related Outputs

- **D6:** Post-custodial Toolkit
- **P4:** Post-Custodial Archival Management

Project Outputs

Pipeline (D1)

The project's AI pipeline enables Named Entity Recognition, Entity Linking, and Relation Extraction on CGDC, providing community organisations with a means to enrich their materials and have these materials made cross-searchable with other archival content.

[OHOS - GitHub](#)

Observatory (D2)

The project Observatory provides an open resource for public to access previously unsearchable CGDC metadata to discover digital objects held locally and search these materials alongside one another and TNA's Discovery catalogue, and Manage Your Collections. Seven community archives' materials are searchable through the Observatory, alongside materials held by TNA, and across the UK.

The Observatory can be found at <http://ohos.ac.uk>.

Remixer Tools (D3)

Attached to the project Observatory, our Remixer Tools allow for community materials in the Observatory to be viewed and explored in different ways. Three key tools are provided: a timeline view, allowing for examination of content based on chronological data; a map view, allowing for exploration based on geographical data; and a 'tag' view, allowing users to explore entities within materials.

These can be found on the OHOS Observatory, at <http://ohos.ac.uk>.

Prototype Approaches to Semantic Crosswalks (D4)

Semantic Integration in the OHOS Observatory

OHOS combined advanced Natural Language Processing techniques from computer science with detailed expertise and specialised resources from the humanities to create an AI metadata enrichment pipeline for CGDC from our partner community organisations. This enriched data was then used by our partners at The National Archives (TNA) in an open Observatory, where it is the basis of remixing and semantic linkage, including through a prototype Knowledge Graph accessible as a SPARQL Endpoint.

The data from the pipeline has also been used to develop two additional project outputs, not originally in scope: a Wikibase for CGDC, and visualisations of post-pipeline data.

Visualisations of Data Relationships for Distant Reading

Visualisations of collections data have been created that show relationships between people, places, organisations, and events, enabling a new understanding of the interplay between items of community heritage. These visualisations can also show the preponderance of key concepts as indicators of what “matters” to the communities that use digital collections to showcase their heritage and tell their stories.

This image is from our partner community archive, The Morrab Library in Penzance, and shows a sports team at the Penzance County Grammar School for Boys. The Morrab Library metadata describing this item has been enriched by our AI pipeline and will be accessible through our OHOS Observatory.

Fig. 7: Penzance County Grammar School for Boys Athletics Team 1958. Copyright Morrab Library.

In the screenshot below, we showcase a dynamic network visualisation that illustrates the relationships among entities extracted from the archive metadata using the NLP pipeline. This network highlights the connections between people, places, organisations, and events within the Morrab Library. A key hub in this network is the Penzance County Grammar School for Boys as seen in the archival material above, which links to numerous former students, staff, and other local schools and events. By exploring archives through these networks, we can engage with community knowledge in innovative ways.

Fig. 8: Dynamic network visualisation illustrating the relationships among entities extracted from the archive metadata using the NLP pipeline. Courtesy of Hanna Schmück.

Community Heritage Wikibase

Another key output is the OHOS Wikibase of CGDC developed by our partners at the National Library of Wales. This is an alternative destination for CGDC that has been through the pipeline, and has been established as a sustainable output that gives greater access to CGDC. Guidelines for using this as an output have been developed for community organisations (Cf: Cardiff workshop (W7), January 2025).

The Wikibase Instance is a specialised tool and experimental approach to metadata crosswalks in the context of CGDC, providing community organisations with the capacity to create and manage their own Knowledge Graphs and connect these materials with similar resources. While not classified as a core output, it holds substantial potential utility as a model for future community archives to follow to create their own Wikibase instance for sustaining their materials in an accessible form. Managed by the National Library of Wales (NLW), the instance may be made accessible to original data holders for takedown or maintenance. These discussions around takedown and maintenance highlight the need for adaptive strategies to balance sustainability with data stewardship and stakeholder access.

CGDC Research Studies (D5)

Extensive explorations of different use cases for CGDC were produced by the project's History Lab: Community-Generated Digital Content and the Hidden Music-Makers of Late Twentieth-Century Britain (<https://zenodo.org/records/11262741>); Conversations on communities, digital content and the professional historian (<https://zenodo.org/records/14756441>); Community Generated Digital Content and the Postmemory of the Second World War (<https://zenodo.org/records/11244081>); CGDC and 'composure' in Black and Asian stories of late twentieth-century Britain (<https://zenodo.org/records/11262957>); CGDC and Disability Rights in the later 20th century (<https://zenodo.org/records/11262819>); A free resource for all? Legal and ethical considerations when using CGDC for research (<https://zenodo.org/records/11262943>).

Studies into CGDC were also produced by project partners:

- NLS case studies: OurStory Scotland Collection, <https://zenodo.org/records/14796179>, Cinema Sgìre Project (<https://zenodo.org/records/14753701> and Modus Arts Tape Letters Scotland (<https://zenodo.org/records/14795874>).
- Tate case studies developed for their workshop, "The Archive as a Gathering Place" <https://zenodo.org/records/14750338>
- Manchester Histories report, showcasing Greater Manchester Coalition of Disabled People, Park Friends, Manchester Digital Music Archive, and Manchester Hip Hop Archive <https://zenodo.org/records/11221641>

Journal Articles

Further CGDC research study outputs took the form of journal articles and book chapters published throughout the lifetime of the project, with these listed below in relation to each of the project's Labs.

All Labs

- Our Heritage, Our Stories: *developing AI tools to link and support community-generated digital cultural heritage*. Hannaford, E. D., Schlegel, V., Lewis, R., Ramsden, S., Bunn, J., Moore, J., Alexander, M., Barker, H., Batista-Navarro, R., Hughes, L., Nenadic, G. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/jd-03-2024-0057/full/html>

AI Lab & Linguistics workstream

- Enriching the Metadata of Community-Generated Digital Content through Entity Linking: An Evaluative Comparison of State-of-the-Art Models. Benkhedda, Y., Skapars, A., Schlegel, V., Nenadic, G. & Batista-Navarro, R. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.latechclfl-1.20.pdf>
- Integrating Community-Generated Digital Content into the UK National Collection. Benkhedda, Y., Skapars, A., Schlegel, V., Nenadic, G. & Batista-Navarro, R. <https://cudan.tlu.ee/conference/CUDAN2023-abstract-69.pdf>
- Relation Extraction for Constructing Knowledge Graphs: Enhancing the Searchability of Community-Generated Digital Content (CGDC) Collections. Marinov, M., Benkhedda, Y.,

Hannaford, E. D., Alexander, M., Nenadic, G. & Batista-Navarro, R.

<https://openreview.net/pdf?id=ZOKivqgTjg>

- *Refining Predicates for Relation Extraction through Thesaurus Integration*. Hannaford, E. D., Benkhedda, Y., Alexander, M., Nenadic, G. & Batista-Navarro, R. <https://www.utwente.nl/en/eemcs/fois2024/resources/papers/hannaford-et-al-refining-predicates-for-relation-extraction-through-thesaurus-integration.pdf>
- Linguistic diversity in institutional collections: Beyond preservation to valorisation. Hannaford, E. D. & Alexander, M. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10475280>
- Co-creation and the digital archive: unlocking historic archives and records through new approaches to mass digitisation. Hughes, L.M. <https://global.oup.com/academic/product/archival-materialities-in-a-digital-age-9780197267851?lang=en&cc=re#>

History Lab

- Deindustrialisation and digital remembrance in Hull's former fishing community. Ramsden, S. & Barker, H. [forthcoming]
- First person narratives of race relations in late twentieth-century Britain. Ramsden, S. & Barker, H. [forthcoming]
- Our Heritage, Our Stories: Valuing and accessing UK digital citizen history. Barker, H. & Ramsden, S. History Workshop. <https://www.historyworkshop.org.uk/digital-history/uk-digital-citizen-history/>.

Post-Custodial Toolkit (D6)

The Post-Custodial Toolkit provides community organisations with the means to effectively manage their own materials, adhering to a post-custodial approach that emphasises the importance of communities maintaining curatorial control over their own resources. It is hosted by the Digital Preservation Coalition, here: <https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/implement-digipres/community-archives-dp-toolkit>.

White papers (D7)

- **P1:** Saving UK CGDC at Risk
- **P2:** Metadata Crosswalks Beyond Discovery
- **P3:** Emerging Approaches to Data Aggregation and Rights
- **P4:** Post-Custodial Archival Management
- **P5:** Language as a Heritage Object
- **P6:** Ethical Use of AI in Community Contexts

Workshops

- **W1:** Project Start-Up
Complete as per bid (10/12/2021)
- **W2:** CGDC Producers
Split into W2A (NLS workshop, 23/04/2024) and W2B (PRONI Workshop, 11/06/2024)

- **W3:** Evaluating Reuse
Y2 York Kick-off meeting (21/06/2022)
- **W4:** Remixing Tool
Done as internal workshop where Investigators/RAs discussed the Visualization Tools for the Observatory (13/02/2024)
- **W5:** Historian Engagement
Run with Manchester Histories in Spring 2023 and ongoing engagement at conferences and dissemination activity.
- **W6:** Post-Custodial Approaches
- Split into W6A (iPres Conference panel discussion on 17/09/2024) and W6B (Capturing Language and Dialects and Post-Custodial Practice, 06/11/2024 & 09/01/2025)
- **W7:** AI Pipeline: Producers & Users
NLW workshop in Cardiff, additional focus on Wikibase (15/01/2025)
- **W8:** Ethics & Data Sharing Models
Split to be W8A (attendance at TaNC ethics workshop in Jan 2024), W8B (Tate focus groups in April 2024) & W8C (Tate public events in May 2024)
- **W9:** Language Data and Wikidata
Online YODA workshop (16/07/2024)
- **W10:** Post-Custodial Toolkit (ALT and CAHG)
- **W11:** BYO CGDC Datathon (February 2024)
Changed to be a series of targeted data-gathering exercises with community archives that decided to include their cataloguing metadata into the creation and development of the Observatory. (W11A – W11F)
W11A BYO CGDC Datathon - Milton Keynes City Discovery Centre
W11B BYO CGDC Datathon - Sharing Wycombe's Old Photographs
W11C BYO CGDC Datathon – Surrey History Centre
W11D BYO CGDC Datathon - People's Collection Wales
W11E BYO CGDC Datathon - The Morrab Library
W11F BYO CGDC Datathon - CAIN
- **W12:** Closing Symposium
Split into W12A (World Digital Preservation Day 07-08/11/2024 and W12B (Public engagement event with Being Human Festival on 09/11/2024).

Other Outputs

Other outputs include network visualisations of partner metadata; activities reports, policy facing outputs, calls to action, blog posts, and a series of reports from our collaborating network/community of practice. These are all available on the OHOS website or on Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/communities/ohos/>.

Cross Project Collaboration

The TaNC programme organised a range of meetings across the projects. These included nine cross-programme meetings, all but one online, and two programme conferences (26/04/2023; 20&21/11/24). Additionally, the project had meetings with the TaNC Directorate on five occasions, where updates were provided about relevant programme activities and synergies. All of these discussions focused more on sharing updates and plenary discussions than in facilitating cross-project collaboration, with little flexible time and space to develop plans, and so were of limited utility in terms of collaboration, although had other objectives to fulfil.

In January 2024 OHOS participated in the *Ethics as Practice* workshop, which brought together representatives from the Discovery Projects and the TaNC Directorate to explore ethical concerns and develop recommendations for policy and practice. OHOS project team members also took part in the TaNC programme's Communicating Colonial Legacies Workshop in May 2022.

In spring 2024 Ashleigh Hawkins (OHOS) and Dr Anna-Maria Sichani (Congruence Engine) initiated a focus group as a forum to discuss and exchange experiences, challenges and potential solutions on issues around data documentation, processing, archiving and publication, and practice developed across TaNC Discovery projects. In July 2024 a focus group meeting brought together representatives of each of the five TaNC Discovery projects and members of the TaNC Directorate to enable targeted discussions that formed the basis for a series of recommendations about project planning, budgeting, recruitment, as well as the need for advocacy of robust data documentation and management practices and for centralised investment in digital data infrastructure.

The investigators and PIs of a number of TaNC projects were in regular contact to discuss the coordination of common issues and queries, the challenges of operating within the overarching programme framework, and other matters of common concern. These were organised informally and flexibly but took place online and in person throughout the three years, and have led to plans for future activities. PI collaboration and data sharing was an important part of research processes and sharing good practice. Additionally, investigators from OHOS and the Sloane Lab project came together to discuss good practice in AI and cultural heritage drawing on experience across both projects.

Sustainability and Infrastructure

The OHOS project has produced an extremely diverse range of outputs, encompassing technical, social, and systemic developments in the management and preservation of CGDC. As such, this diversity of outputs requires a similarly diverse infrastructure for sustaining them, tailored to the nature of each of them. The following outlines plans for maintaining OHOS deliverables, beyond the lifetime of the project, to ensure that community organisations, researchers, and the public can continue to benefit from the project's work and deliverables.

AI Pipeline (D1)

The AI Pipeline is a significant technical output, representing a collection of workflows and tools designed to process, analyse, and generate insights from project data. The sustainability plan involves hosting these tools on GitHub, managed by the AI Lab. This approach ensures that the pipeline, or components of it, can be reused or adapted by other projects or stakeholders. While there is no strict mandate for its preservation, sustaining the pipeline is considered good practice. Efforts have been focused on modularising the pipeline so individual tools can be used independently, enhancing its utility and longevity. Processes for managing any personal information within the pipeline are under development, ensuring compliance with data protection standards. The pipeline's sustainability ensures continuity for future AI-driven research initiatives, leveraging its tools and methodologies.

Observatory (D2)

The Observatory represents a critical project output, intended to provide ongoing value by offering a structured and accessible platform for its data and insights. To ensure its longevity, it will be managed by The National Archives (TNA) for at least three years following the conclusion of funding. A crucial component of its sustainability plan is the creation of a static snapshot or record, which will be archived in the Government Web Archive. This ensures not only its accessibility to researchers and stakeholders but also its compliance with public archiving standards. The exact parameters for its long-term maintenance, including data handling and protection measures, have been refined through data-sharing agreements and a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). These processes address legal and ethical considerations, particularly concerning sensitive data or personal information. This ensures the Observatory's transition into a static resource aligns with regulatory requirements and best practices in digital preservation.

Remixer Tools (D3)

The Remixer Tools, integral to the project's technical infrastructure, facilitate user interaction with data. Like the Observatory, their sustainability will be overseen by TNA for three years post-funding. Their association with the Observatory ensures their preservation indirectly through the inclusion of the Observatory's snapshot in the Government Web Archive. This approach ensures the tools' contributions to the project's

broader outcomes remain accessible, even if standalone functionality is not sustained. The role of these tools in enabling interactive engagement with the data highlights their significance as part of the project's technical legacy.

OHOS Community Heritage Wikibase (D4)

The OHOS Wikibase Instance is a specialised tool and experimental approach to metadata crosswalks in the context of CGDC, providing community organisations with the capacity to create and manage their own Knowledge Graphs and connect these materials with similar resources. While not classified as a core output, it holds substantial potential utility as a model for future community archives to follow to create their own Wikibase instance for sustaining their materials in an accessible form. Managed by the National Library of Wales (NLW), the instance may be made accessible to original data holders for takedown or maintenance. These discussions highlight the need for adaptive strategies to balance sustainability with data stewardship and stakeholder access.

Peer-reviewed Publications (D5)

As scholarly outputs, peer-reviewed publications hold significant weight in ensuring the project's academic credibility and legacy. These publications are listed on the OHOS website, with detailed links to their respective Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), ensuring discoverability and ease of access. Open Access (OA) publication strategies were prioritised, reflecting the project's commitment to making its research freely available to a broad audience. The sustainability of these publications as static core outputs guarantees their continued availability for academic referencing and practical application, reinforcing the project's contribution to advancing knowledge in its field.

Post-Custodial Toolkit (D6)

The Post-Custodial Toolkit is a key resource for practitioners and stakeholders, offering guidance on managing digital archives in a post-custodial model for use by community organisations and other interested parties. It is preserved in two formats: a static version for long-term reference and an interactive version hosted on the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) website. By storing the toolkit in the Zenodo repository, the project ensures its secure preservation and accessibility. The DPC will oversee management of the interactive version, ensuring the toolkit remains a valuable and dynamic resource for practitioners navigating digital preservation challenges.

Fig. 9: Left: Digital Preservation Toolkit for Community Archives Cover Page. Source: Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC).

Fig. 10: Right: Panel discussion during World Digital Preservation Day, where the toolkit was launched. Source: Nella McNicol

White Papers (D7)

White papers are core outputs, functioning as comprehensive documents that consolidate the project's research, findings, and recommendations. These are preserved in static form and hosted across multiple platforms, including the Glasgow Institutional Repository, the project website, and Zenodo. The creation of DOIs for each white paper ensures these papers are easily discoverable and citable, enhancing their academic and practical impact. Their interconnection with other outputs—such as blogs, workshops, and additional reports—creates a robust framework for knowledge dissemination. By sustaining these papers, the project ensures that its intellectual contributions remain accessible and relevant to researchers, policymakers, and practitioners for years to come.

CPD Activities

Continuing Professional Development (CPD) activities have been identified as outcomes of a number of activities developed in collaboration with partner activities. Many community fund activities resulted in professional training and development for those working in the heritage sector (for example, workshops by the Rural Community Network, the John and Pat Hume Foundation, and GAMIS/Offline), designed to support stakeholders. We have also left a legacy of documentation and outputs that will be supported by our partners particularly in areas such as rights and community-generated digital collections, including NLW (supporting further uptake of the CGDC Wikibase) and DPC (which will carry out post-project activities embedding the post-custodial toolkit into community and indigenous heritage practice internationally). Further, Information Studies at the University of Glasgow will embed project outputs into the departments popular micro credentials for archives professionals, evidencing the project's commitment to distributing project outputs to ensure the continuation of professional learning opportunities. This is part of the OHOS sustainability strategy highlighting the project's dedication to fostering ongoing education and capacity-building within its community of practice.

Workshop Reports

Workshop reports capture the insights, discussions, and outcomes of the project's interactive events. These reports not only contributed to the development of white papers but also serve as standalone records of the project's engagement with stakeholders. To sustain these outputs, they are archived in static form on the Glasgow Institutional Repository and the project website. DOIs generated via Zenodo further enhance their visibility and accessibility. These reports provide valuable documentation of the project's participatory approach and its contributions to fostering dialogue and collaboration within its community.

Community Fund

The Community Fund's outputs include diverse materials such as films, pamphlets, podcasts, and promotional resources, documenting the project's outreach and engagement efforts. These materials are preserved as static outputs on the OHOS website and the University of Glasgow Institutional Repository. This ensures that the cultural and educational value of these outputs is retained, providing resources for future projects, community initiatives, and public engagement. By capturing the breadth of the Community Fund's activities,

the project ensures that its contributions to community engagement and capacity-building are documented and accessible.

Project Website

The project website serves as the central hub for disseminating blogs, white papers, and other reports. Managed by the University of Glasgow for at least three years post-funding, it will continue to host these outputs to ensure their accessibility. Policies prohibiting the inclusion of personal information on the website align with best practices in data protection and enhance the site's sustainability. By maintaining the website as a repository of project outputs, the project secures its digital presence and accessibility for a diverse audience.

Grey Literature

Grey literature encompasses a wide range of project-generated materials, including community metadata records, case studies, reports, interview documentation, and software repositories. These outputs are preserved in static form by the University of Glasgow, ensuring a comprehensive record of the project's data-gathering, activities and insights.

The OHOS sustainability strategy emphasises the importance of documenting not only the project's formal outputs but also its broader context and methodologies. By sustaining the grey literature created by the project OHOS leaves a valuable resource for future research, policy-making, and practical application.

Final Recommendations

OHOS has developed key approaches and outputs that connect, harmonise, link and share CGDC metadata as part of the national collection. We have built a greater understanding of how our national story is shaped by the hidden histories in CGDC, and how this data can contribute to research across the disciplines. We have also developed, for the first time, an in-depth analysis of the practice and systems for creating CGDC and preserving it over the long term.

Below, we make recommendations for future areas of research and development that will further CGDC as part of the digital research ecosystem and the creative economy, unlocking greater innovation across the UK's digital infrastructure for collections and research.

These recommendations draw on our evidence gathering and research, and encompass technical, computational and infrastructural aspects, including recommendations about the creation, management and use of CGDC that will enable this data to have a long-term legacy that best represents the communities that create and use it and infrastructural recommendations about the structures and investment needed at a national level to deliver the promise of CGDC in a national collection.

Our keystone recommendation is for an improved sense of the importance of community heritage amongst decision makers and the present and future role of archives in our national story. CGDC data is precious and irreplaceable, and it needs to be recognised as such by funders, the research community and the public. At present, the community archives sector is woefully underfunded and runs on goodwill, and too often, community and local archives do not receive the funding, resources, or attention and support available to other large heritage organisations. In spite of this lack of resourcing, the achievements across the UK community heritage sector are phenomenal and when set in context with the collections of large national bodies, CGDC is genuinely transformative when it comes to our national historical narrative. We therefore recommend that as part of work on a national collection, **greater funding should be allocated to the digital ambitions of the community heritage sector**, especially in terms of ensuring its long-term sustainability.

A second fundamental recommendation draws on our research that brought together historians, linguists, computer sciences and digital humanists. There is missed potential in many major funded projects that are potentially transformative for many disciplines. We need a future digital infrastructure that integrates digital resources and conceptualises them as multipurpose and re-useable collections open to all disciplines.

Archival Recommendations

- As stated above, funding for the community archives and heritage sector is extremely limited and most importantly, not sustained or consistent: and yet, these organisations deal with some of the most digitally complex, fragile, and vulnerable-to-loss archival collections in the heritage sector. There is a need for community heritage organisations to work with funders to **identify what support is needed on an ongoing (not project based) basis, and to work together on business cases with organisations and government departments that provide that support**. Funders of community heritage organisations should consider urgently the funding or a network of permanent posts with a remit to support digital activities across a regional network as a collective approach to share responsibility and expertise. This could underpin structural reviews of extant

data; implementing retention, selection and disposal policies for historic archives as well as newly generated ones; networking and collaborating with other organisations to pool resources; providing training to volunteers; and engaging in contemporary collecting practices.

- CGDC is critically vulnerable, and the broader community needs to work together with common purpose to prevent the irreparable loss of CGDC content; by identifying the knowledge and resources that are required; the leadership needed to champion CGDC; and by developing a set of replicable actions throughout the digital lifecycle that **always embed long-term preservation** into the creation of digital resources.
- While greater support is urgently needed for the creation, management and long-term preservation of CGDC, there is a need for models that enable ‘meeting communities where they are at’, which are embedded in community practice and sympathetic to the digital ecosystems of community heritage, and which can be flexible to specific demands/requirements/capacities of different community groups. Top-down approaches to mandates for good practice are not widely utilised or effective. **Adopting the post-custodial model** developed by OHOS addresses the need for grassroots-led archival management activities.
- Community heritage organisations contribute a great deal of value, not just in the resources they make available for education and research, but in the services they provide to communities. They are often hubs for memory activities, and by making people aware of their sense of place they can build inclusive communities. We encourage all community heritage organisations to **embed within the documentation the added value of their existence to the communities they support, and actively generate quantitative and qualitative data in consistent forms** that can be understood across different types of funders.
- Everything is a metadata problem, and if that works, things fall into place. Metadata supports community archive needs to document and describe their data to the widest audiences over the long term. Rich metadata is also essential to appropriately and sensitively present data out of context: when CGDC is shared and presented outside of its original community archive context, there is a risk that data will be included that is difficult to understand or situate, or that data taken out of context seems sensitive, inappropriate, or even offensive. If the aim is to be as inclusive as possible, and not exclude sensitive data, the question of how to present it to a user in an interface needs to be considered. Without recreating a community archive’s website, it is difficult to determine how much contextual information is required to adequately situate an item in context, and technically challenging to apply this automatically and at scale. **Community archives need access to consistent, open, and free training in cataloguing and description. Sector organisations that offer face-to-face training – Archives & Records Association (ARA), Community Archives and Heritage Group (CAGH), and TNA - should be funded to develop a consultation activity to ensure that the training they offer is consistent and appropriate**, and ideally ARA accredited as appropriate.
- Plan ahead rather than look back: once a project is complete, it is often too late to consider how the CGDC’s longevity will be safeguarded as decisions regarding technical and legal aspects have already been made and resources have already been expended. **Funding bodies need to take responsibility for forward planning of CGDC they have funded, and ensure that infrastructure and guidance is in place to support informed decisions on the structure and format as well as data collection, management and preservation strategies before any content is created.** There are three main strands that come together to help ensure effective management and preservation

of digital collections. They are Technology, Management, and Resources. Without some work in all these areas, preservation of digital collections in any group or organisation won't be possible. Ultimately, digital preservation is about making an investment in properly managing digital collections with common sense, consistency and an attention to detail. Careful planning for digital preservation will safeguard assets and avoid the need for costly intervention further down the line. In addition, documenting archival practice, and why specific approaches were used, will help anyone who needs to preserve a legacy digital collection in the future.

- **A scoping exercise should be funded by NLHF or AHRC to explore how community archives can better leverage existing digital infrastructure for community heritage**, especially local council funded records office, the UK Web Archive, National Libraries, and organisations like CAHG. These organisations should work on outreach strategies for Community Heritage.
- Post-custodial approaches to archival management are highly appropriate for CGDC. They give power and control back to the data holders and creators, and are an opportunity for liminal approaches to archive management. OHOS outputs can be used as a template for these models, **further training and support for post-custodial approaches in archives should be embedded into archival education and professional training.**
- There is an urgent need for transparent models and practices for working with GDPR in the community heritage sector. **Funding should be available for access to training and advice on GDPR for community heritage.**
- **There is an urgent need for curatorial guidance to be developed on working with multilingual and multidialectal content** – asking community archives to ‘translate’ dialect terms can be disrespectful and erases the lived experience of archives and local expertise. This is particularly acute in areas (generally areas with significant working-class populations) where the use of local dialect is seen as ‘slang’ or is otherwise denigrated by staff from official organisations. Linguists have expertise in this area to support archival practitioners, while archives have rich and detailed experience of local situated knowledge to exchange with linguists who have a need for contextual data for dialects. There are therefore rich cross-exchange potentials here for the benefit of communities.
- There is no national registry or catalogue of CGDC. Manage Your Collections provides access to information about a large number of collections and collecting organisations, but does not contain information about digital items. An archival equivalent of the Museum Data Service could address this gap. **CGDC needs “a place on the map”.**

Recommendations for Researchers Working with CGDC Materials

- **Clearer models and processes for rights management should be developed, maintained, and shared.** AHRC and national bodies with responsibility for training and the archival sector should put in place an upskilling programme for community archives on copyright regulations.
- **There is an urgent need for transparent models and practices for working with GDPR in the community heritage sector**, for both researchers and heritage staff, and for better support in developing data sharing models/agreements.
- **Researchers should integrate and document ethical considerations into every stage of the research process when working with CGDC**, and reflect on the potential harm and benefits their work may bring. It is vital to engage with stakeholders, particularly those whose work and

identities are represented in CGDC, to understand their perspectives and concerns. While it may not always be necessary to seek informed consent for the use of CGDC, researchers should always consider the wishes of the individuals involved in the creation and representation of the content. For university-based researchers, there is an additional layer of responsibility. They must ensure their research adheres to institutional ethical frameworks, which may require formal peer ethical review before using CGDC materials. In this way, the guidance calls for a thoughtful, multifaceted approach to using these valuable resources, balancing legal requirements, ethical considerations, and institutional policies.

- Community heritage should be encouraged to **add descriptions of access restrictions as part of the metadata.**

Technical Recommendations

- Data models for CGDC can be simple and layered: **minimal metadata is often sufficient** to make CGDC findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (**FAIR**). However, as many entities as possible should be included in documentation, if necessary in the keywords field of a metadata record, to facilitate rich entity linking and search. These entities can be added and validated by curators and/or AI.
- Wherever possible, **open formats/standards** should be used for AI/Machine Learning approaches, and any tools or outputs should be made accessible with accompanying documentation and, if possible, training materials.
- **Cross-council development work should be funded** to generate more sophisticated AI tools that can detect and handle personal data in diverse and non-standard formats, with multidialectal CGDC being a particularly fruitful testbed for complex humanities data.
- Technical solutions for CGDC should **develop more frameworks for privacy-first design**, with it being imperative that automated systems integrate tools to identify and manage personal data, ensuring compliance with regulations including GDPR. As archives increasingly contribute data from the 20th and 21st centuries, giving essential context to recent local and national challenges, addressing these privacy concerns will be crucial to maintaining trust and inclusivity and gaining access to this rich data.
- Any national collection for CGDC needs to **establish standards for processes to maintain and re-ingest data over time**, accommodating the fact that community heritage organisations update their collections and data as resources allow, meaning that more content is added, and new descriptions are created. Processes will need to be established to maintain up-to-date versions with version tracking and to enable incremental updates rather than full re-uploads in order to maintain links to enriched data already uploaded. This will also ensure compliance with GDPR by preventing the publication of personal data that a community archive has removed from their dataset since the data was aggregated. Keeping abreast of data changes over time and at scale in an automated fashion is a significant but worthwhile challenge.
- Using open-access, widely-used content (such as Wikidata) as the basis for Relation Extraction shows that there is a need for **better use of existing ontologies, authority data, and catalogue data** for the use of AI validation of cultural heritage metadata. A rich ecosystem of data exists that could be re-purposed into large language models for CGDC and related heritage content.

- To enable users to have direct access to the digital objects described in the aggregated metadata, the use of unique URIs to digital objects and their associated metadata items online should be encouraged by **funding a national URI service free at the point of use**. Beyond this, national organisations carrying out aggregation of heritage data at scale as part of a national collection should review their existing technical architecture and systems for adaptation to data to be aggregated. It is always more sustainable to work with existing, tested and robust infrastructure rather than building bespoke solutions. Digital humanities researchers contributing their expertise to a national collection should become more aware of the existing landscape of technical investment, and explore its applicability to the affordances of digital innovation around linking and discovery.

Structural/Systemic Recommendations

- **A radical rethink of the funding environment for digital infrastructure for digital heritage is essential.** Existing support for CGDC development and preservation varies broadly in longevity and depth and lacks overall cohesion; projects are almost always funded on a short-term basis without consideration of sustainability requirements for the long-term preservation of and access to the digital outputs they generate. Funders also have generally moved away from small grants, which can be transformative for individual archives, due to the administration cost of each grant. The UK infrastructure for community heritage therefore lacks sustainable, permanent specialist staff contracts; longer-term budget security and funding; clear and consistent advice from experts, including standardised best practice guidelines; and clearer structure and strategy across the organisations. **Funding put in place for community archives should incorporate considerations of how this data can become part of a national collection.**
- **Across the UK, there is a need for strengthened local and national structure-building for community heritage, and more powerful voices to advocate for what is needed** to ensure the required support, time and resourcing are identified and provided, and that existing and identified skills gaps in digital data are addressed across the community heritage sector.
- **A UK data infrastructure that supports the preservation, use and re-use of CGDC is urgently required.** This includes a shared and easily accessible digital repository for digital outputs of community heritage, a searchable access point for local assets, and a methods and tools interface for creative and research use of the data.
- A national collection requires the facilitation of deep collaboration between large national bodies (including IROs), sector bodies which are not research organisations, and universities. Work in this area requires incorporating at a deep and structural level an understanding of what these organisations can contribute in terms of complementary expertise and what their own local drivers and institutional priorities are. Cultural work should be done to scope the nature of these bodies as collaborators in research in order to **build workable future frameworks for fruitful large-scale collaboration**. This includes an appraisal of the underpinning legal and operational frameworks, for example those under which HEIs and civil service organisations are allowed to process and publish data.
- **Funders should provide frameworks for funding collaborations with small organisations that may be self-organising and volunteer-led over long timescales**, working in ways that may not be

consistent with the timeframes and requirements of UKRI and nationally funded projects (for example, community organisations reliant on volunteer labour have to work in modular, seasonal, and incremental ways).

- There is a need for explicitly funded local and national networks working alongside strategic and targeted funded initiatives to ensure proper futureproofing of critically endangered CGDC across the UK, in the form of a national network of practice in CGDC. A joined-up strategy and vision needs to be set out to ensure the correct contacts and connections are made between local groups and established institutions, and it is imperative that the specifics, structures, and contingencies of the community heritage context are considered and embedded in this strategy. Additional support is required across the sector to enable a joined-up strategic approach that will encourage stable, long-term funding, with facilitated training courses and pooled organisational resources. The strategy must ensure a diverse range of voices, communities and stories are represented in the CGDC which is preserved for future generations, and sensitivity around the collecting and representation of material which may be traumatic or contested.

Recommendations for Future Projects

Further recommendations have been developed by OHOS about the ways that large, interdisciplinary projects that are infrastructural in nature should be developed and funded.

- The start-up time for multi-disciplinary, multi partner and pan-institutional projects is significant. Space for this should be factored into the design of future funding schemes, with **a fully funded preparation phase of at least three months to provide investigators and project managers the space to establish necessary legal and infrastructural groundwork, including hiring project staff.** In addition, complex and multi-partner projects can face epistemological differences from the start and so we recommend projects and funding schemes hold early, dedicated workshops addressing this issue. This startup phase should also address questions of data sharing and integration from ethical and rights perspective, and the legal basis for data sharing, data processing, and data controlling. **Legal time frames and iteration need to be factored into every project that shares data across organisations.**
- Even a large-scale project will by necessity have only a small team of people working on it at each organisation, meaning that projects can themselves become silos, and gatekeeping can occur. **All team members and partners should be encouraged to talk to anyone in their institution they find might be interesting or useful,** and do the same in return, early in the project life cycle.
- It is important to always **be blunt and honest with your funder** especially if there are problems on a project. OHOS had an excellent funder, but the organisation of the wider programme could have benefitted from, and would have welcomed, feedback about what the projects needed. It is important to remember that funders learn from every project they fund.
- Failures on projects tell us just as much about successes. **Projects in the arts and humanities should be encouraged to write about failure, blog about failure, reward where people talk about failure in formal reports, and celebrate negative results.** Digital humanities is a field reaching maturity, we must celebrate that failure means our colleagues aimed high and ambitiously, and conversely that consistent success is a marker of a project aiming for the easy middle ground.

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References

All project documents and datasets are located on Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/communities/ohos/>.